

DOES GOD INTERVENE IN WARFARE?

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Abstract:

This dissertation explores whether the Christian God intervenes in warfare and examines reasons for such intervention or its absence. It evaluates Augustinian just war theory, including *Jus ad Bellum* (justice of war) and *Jus in Bello* (justice in war), and contrasts it with Christian pacifism, highlighting the tension between the two. It investigates the coherence between the New and Old Testaments regarding God's role in warfare and explores when, if ever, Christians may use divinely sanctioned violence. The metaphysical aspects of divine intervention are considered, as well as a modern Christian near-death experience as a potential source of insight. Additionally, case studies of Christian soldiers from the First and Second World Wars are analyzed for possible evidence of divine intervention, assessing both the reasons and methods of God's involvement in warfare.

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Introduction

Does God intervene in warfare? In this dissertation, references to ‘God’ are shorthand for the Christian God, as revealed in both the Old Testament (OT) and New Testament (NT) of the Holy Bible. At times, the nature of God as revealed in OT and NT may seem contradictory. The God of the OT could be perceived as generally *wrathful*,¹ while the God of the NT is often portrayed in contrasting terms, characterized by grace and gentleness as revealed in the person of Jesus Christ.² In fact, there are numerous examples which depict God’s wrath in the OT;³ and contrastingly the God of the NT exemplified in Jesus Christ who promoted pacifism in many fundamental respects, as embodied in the magnanimous spirit of turning the other cheek.⁴ A cursory inspection of both books may lead a scholar to wonder if the God of the OT is the same as the God of the NT. However, comprehensive analysis would lead the scholar to a more comprehensive view that both books depict a divine nature which is both loving and just, which demonstrates God’s multidimensionality. It could be argued that God is

¹ Isa. 13:9 KJV. OT Example: “Behold, the day of the LORD cometh, cruel both with wrath and fierce anger, to lay the land desolate: and he shall destroy the sinners thereof out of it.”

² Matt. 5:39. “But I say unto you, That ye resist not evil: but whosoever shall smite thee on thy right cheek, turn to him the other also.”

³ Gen. 6:7; Gen. 19:24-29; Exod. 9:13-15; Nah. 1:2-6; Ps. 75:8; Ezek. 25:17.

⁴ Matt. 11:28-30; Mark 10:47-52; Luke 6:27; John 6:51-58; John 8:12; John 10:10; John 15:11-13.

fundamentally like any good parent who is both loving and strict, and whose divine admonishment is thought to be based in love and humanity's ultimate flourishing. Similarly, Jesus Christ as depicted in the NT is the embodiment of divine love yet appears to have no tolerance for unrepentant wickedness and unrighteousness.⁵

Therefore, can a coherent picture of God's divine position on warfare be discerned based on scholarly analysis of the Holy Bible? Moreover, could it be established that divine intervention in warfare by God is compatible with the NT as well as the OT, and has continued even until the modern era? If so, how can the seemingly pacifist ideas of Jesus Christ as revealed in the NT be reconciled with Christians employing violence as warfare? It might be that Christian just war theory and Christian pacifism are both right in the sense of being contextually and situationally right. It might be that both concepts push against the other in a type of *Golden Mean*⁶ where the use of violence is restrained and tempered by divine wisdom but not altogether eliminated as a viable option when necessary.

Further comparative analysis of the NT and OT might be able to reconcile any perceived disparity between the two books in terms of God's divine intervention in warfare, and examples of such intervention in the OT are arguably not invalidated or supplanted by NT concepts; even though the NT provides additional revealed insights regarding divine justice and when the use of violence might be justified either by God, or men, in accordance with God's divine

⁵ Matt. 18:6 KJV; Matt. 21:12 KJV.

⁶ Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, trans. Rowe, Christopher and commentary by Sarah Broadie (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2002), 118, 252-253.

principles. For instance, in the OT there are multiple examples of how God intervenes to aid the chosen people and preserve them from their enemies (e.g., “Thou *art* my servant, O Israel... Thus saith the LORD, the Redeemer of Israel;”⁷ “And I will feed them that oppress thee with their own flesh; and they shall be drunken with their own blood, as with sweet wine: and all flesh shall know that I the LORD *am* thy Saviour and thy Redeemer.”⁸ By contrast, it may appear by a cursory inspection that the NT seems to omit such themes altogether, while promoting a pacifistic model, e.g., “That ye resist not evil: but whosoever shall smite thee on thy right cheek, turn to him the other also;”⁹ and “Put up again thy sword into his place: for all they that take the sword shall perish with the sword.”¹⁰ Nevertheless, a more holistic examination of the NT reveals a sharp division of the wicked from the righteous,¹¹ and divine justice as well as violent wrath poured out upon the wicked.¹² Hence, a holistic interpretation of the NT may buttress the Augustinian Christian just war tradition.¹³

⁷ Isa. 49:3-7 KJV.

⁸ Isa. 49:26.

⁹ Matt. 5:39 KJV.

¹⁰ Matt. 26:52 KJV.

¹¹ Matt. 10:34-36 KJV; Matt. 25:32-33 KJV.

¹² Matt. 18:6 KJV; Matt. 25:30 KJV; Matt. 25:41 KJV; Rev. 20:9-10 KJV.

¹³ Nigel Biggar, *In Defence of War* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), 13. Biggar articulates that St “Augustine’s early articulation of just war thinking at the turn of the fourth and fifth centuries is often regarded as the prime symptom of the church’s lapse from its pristine state of grace.”

In this dissertation, I explore whether God intervenes in warfare by analyzing the divine ethics of warfare through the lens of Augustinian just war theory as well as by Christian pacifism. This analysis explores how God might intervene in war without contradicting God's own divine laws, by examining opposing factors that might justify and restrain divine intervention in war. I explore metaphysics of divine intervention as applied to a case study in the OT to evaluate a potential explanation of divine intervention from the perspective of science and reason. I also explore one Christian near-death experience (NDE) as a source of intelligence outside of the Bible which appears to have something to contribute on the topic of God's revealed wisdom regarding warfare. While this might be somewhat unorthodox, I contend that the information obtained is compelling and potentially significant to this topic. Lastly, I analyze two case studies of Christian soldiers in war to identify what might be divine intervention: one from each World War I, and World War II. These may articulate positive arguments for divine intervention in modern warfare under certain conditions.

Due to the scope of the question, I find it necessary to examine selected biblical scripture, but also examine phenomena outside of the Holy Bible in order to examine the question from multiple angles. It could be argued that due to God's ineffable nature intelligence must be gathered from multiple angles in order to even begin the task of examining whether God intervenes in warfare. Just as in a real-world strategic sense a military campaign against a particular country would require intelligence from multiple sources in order for a successful strategy to be developed. Various sources of intelligence would be obtained from satellite

imagery, humans on the ground, electromagnetic signals in the air, etc., and used by military strategists to devise a plan in warfare. In other words, various means are used to obtain knowledge of that which was previously unknown. Similarly, a theologian in determining God's actions might first look to revealed knowledge in the Holy Bible, and then examine various phenomena in the world in order to ascertain whether divine intervention is at work in specific situations; or whether events could be attributed to divine intervention or random probability. This is why I examine both orthodox and novel unorthodox materials in answering the question of whether God intervenes in warfare. In so doing, I attempt to evaluate the *why* and the *how* of God's potential intervention in warfare.

The topic of divine intervention in warfare is not only of historical and biblical significance but also raises profound theological and ethical questions for modern Christians. How can the actions of a God who is described as both loving and just be reconciled with the violence and destruction inherent in war? Furthermore, how do we understand the role of human agency, free will, and divine providence in the context of warfare? These questions are not merely academic; they challenge our perceptions of justice, morality, and the character of God. By examining both Augustinian just war theory and Christian pacifism, this dissertation seeks to navigate these tensions and offer a nuanced understanding of when, if ever, divine intervention in warfare is consistent with Christian teachings. In doing so, it also considers the metaphysical possibility of divine action and how God's will might be manifested in the world through either miraculous events or through the decisions of human actors guided by divine wisdom.

Exploring Christian Just War Theory in the NT Context:

Divine Violence vs. Divine Love

In this section I explore the morality of warfare and examine whether warfare itself is compatible with God as revealed in the NT and whether God could intervene in war without contradicting God's own divine principles. For instance, did the *law of love*¹⁴ revealed by Jesus Christ eliminate the legitimacy of any sort of violence, or conversely bolster the judicious use of violence when skillfully employed to defend the meek and the helpless? This examination will help determine whether violence is justified in certain contexts, and on what basis God might intervene in warfare without contradicting Godself in terms of God's moral and ethical laws. If indeed there are contexts in which violence is divinely justified, then it opens the possibility of God intervening in warfare either directly by divine means, or indirectly by means of governments, societies, and soldiers who are inspired by God's laws, and whose use of violence is tempered by divine wisdom, love, humanity, and restraint.

There is an apparent tension between opposing interpretations of the NT regarding divine violence. The first contends that the NT does not permit the use of violence in any context, even in self-defense following the example of Jesus Christ who offered no armed resistance.¹⁵ The second, asserts that a form of veracious

¹⁴ Mark 12:31 KJV.

¹⁵ Matt. 26:52 KJV.

divine violence is outlined by Jesus Christ in the NT as a form of divine justice against those who harm the meek and innocent.¹⁶

Moreover, the NT illustrates how God might interact with violence regarding the two sinners who were crucified next to Jesus.¹⁷ One mocked Jesus and the other was contrite and asked for forgiveness.¹⁸ The former was shown no mercy, ostensibly ending up in hell, while the latter was taken up into heaven on the same day with Jesus Christ.¹⁹ In this context, the violence of crucifixion is not something God caused for the two sinners, but was the result of their crimes.

Mercy was shown to the contrite sinner in the form of salvation, putting an end to the violence against him postmortem, while there was apparently no end to violence against the second sinner, either in his current life or in the afterlife.²⁰

There is in fact a divine warning about a second death postmortem.²¹ Regarding the NT position on divine violence in warfare, Nigel Biggar contends that “we should think of God as being prepared to respond to incorrigible sinners (should there be any) by authorizing their deaths, not at all because he wants them dead, but because he wants to secure the fulfillment of creation, and because he cannot have the latter

¹⁶ Matt. 18:6 KJV.

¹⁷ Matt. 27:38 KJV; Luke 23:33 KJV.

¹⁸ Luke 23:39-43 KJV.

¹⁹ Luke 23:39-43 KJV.

²⁰ Luke 23:39-43 KJV.

²¹ Rev. 20:14 KJV.

without the former.”²² Therefore, it seems that the NT established both contrasting ideas of divine mercy for the repentant and divine violence for the wicked. The former opens the possibility of divine grace and mercy being poured out to soldiers in warfare who invoke God with contrition and humility while seeking the wisdom to follow God’s will. Therefore, it is possible that God is not always the direct cause of the violence but may provide aid and comfort to soldiers most aligned with His will. This is sort of a negative violence, or rather an amelioration of the effects of violence, which is perhaps granted to the righteous but withheld from the wicked.

By contrast, Christian pacifist scholars such as Richard Hays contend that the NT does not allow any violence, pointing to the *Sermon on the Mount*²³ and more specifically to Matthew 5:38-48²⁴ which ostensibly demonstrates that pacifism is the entire NT ethos.²⁵ However, Nigel Biggar, opposingly, states that Hays erroneously extends pacifism to the NT “as a whole.”²⁶ Moreover, Biggar finds that Hays cherry-picks certain

²² Nigel Biggar, "Specify and Distinguish! Interpreting the New Testament on Non-Violence'," *Studies in Christian ethics* 22, no. 2 (2009): 182.

²³ Richard Hays, *Moral Vision of the New Testament: A Contemporary Introduction To New Testament Ethics* (Edinburgh: T&T Clark, 1997), 320; Matt. Chs. 5-7.

²⁴ Richard Hays, *Moral Vision of the New Testament: A Contemporary Introduction To New Testament Ethics* (Edinburgh: T&T Clark, 1997), 319-20; Matt. 5:38-48.

²⁵ Hays, *Moral Vision of the New Testament*, 319-320; Matt. 5:38-48; Matt. 5-7.

²⁶ Nigel Biggar, "Specify and Distinguish! Interpreting the New Testament on Non-Violence'," *Studies in Christian ethics* 22, no. 2 (2009): 167.

aspects of the NT, conflates, and presents a pacifism-only paradigm of the NT: thus by permitting only certain voices from a choir of voices, Hays constructs, “*the moral vision of the New Testament.*”²⁷ Nonetheless, even if not speaking for the entire NT, there does seem to be ample material in the NT to make the case for Christian pacifism, even if not completely ruling out the necessity for violence in all situations.

While just war theory seeks to justify the use of violence under strict moral conditions, Christian pacifism offers a contrasting paradigm that prioritizes non-violence, even in the face of aggression. Both perspectives, however, find their roots in the ethical teachings of the Bible, particularly in the New Testament’s call to love one’s enemies. The following section will explore the pacifist viewpoint and examine its strengths and potential limitations in the broader discussion of divine intervention in warfare.

The Argument for Christian Pacifism

The argument for Christian pacifism, which more specifically lies in absolute pacifism, is a position which holds that any killing, no matter the situation, including warfare, is morally wrong. There are verses in both the OT and NT which support this position. For instance, Norman Geisler illustrates a biblical argument for Christian pacifism, that, “war is always wrong,”²⁸ found in the OT:

²⁷ Biggar, *In Defence of War*, 35.

²⁸ Normal L. Geisler, *Christian Ethics: Contemporary Issues & Options*, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2010), 225.

“Thou shalt not kill;”²⁹ and in the words of Jesus recorded in the NT as: “That ye resist not evil.”³⁰

Relatedly, G.H.C. MacGregor examines whether Jesus was a pacifist and by extension, the “New Testament basis for pacifism.”³¹ MacGregor points to Matt. 5:17 where Jesus points out that he came not to destroy but fulfill the law and the prophets.³² MacGregor further examines how Jesus’ pacifist ethic redeems from evil by restoring good, and opines that in Jesus “retributive justice which merely checks and punishes evil, is supplanted by active and self-sacrificial love, which redeems and changes the evil will, so ‘vindicating righteousness’ in the only true sense of the word, and thereby ‘fulfilling the law.’”³³ MacGregor by extension contends that the Christian pacifism is grounded the notion that itself is the evil, and that violence only begets more violence, such that relying on violence to end war, “is equivalent to trying to cast out devils by Beelzebub the prince of devils.”³⁴ Contrary to employing violence, MacGregor argues that the Christian pacifist must embody a “positive method of sacrificial and redemptive love, to which as a

²⁹ Geisler, *Christian Ethics*, 225; Exod. 20:13 KJV.

³⁰ Geisler, *Christian Ethics*, 225; Matt. 5:39 KJV.

³¹ G.H.C. MacGregor, “Jesus the Pacifist?,” in *War and Peace*, ed. Jeff Astley, David Brown, and Ann Loades (London, UK: T&T Clark, 2003), 27.

³² MacGregor, “Jesus the Pacifist?,” 27; Matt. 5:17.

³³ MacGregor, “Jesus the Pacifist?,” 28-29.

³⁴ MacGregor, “Jesus the Pacifist?,” 29.

disciple of the Crucified he is called.”³⁵ This sort of model does not appear to make a distinction between Jesus and the individual Christian in terms of embodying a sort of radical pacifism unto martyrdom if necessary.

Other NT scholars, however, interpret the NT differently with respect to the employment of violence. For instance, Arthur Grenke claims that the OT overtly sanctions warfare, while the NT is equivocal and with different interpretations on the topic of warfare.³⁶ Correspondingly, in the next section, I will further explore Christian just war theory and the argument for how divinely sanctioned violence might be justifiable in certain contexts.

Christian Just War Thinking

In terms of Christian just war theory, it seems essential to establish the morality of violence particularly in the NT given its pacifist sentiments, in order to identify coherence of God in relation to the use of violence and the legitimacy of warfare which is perhaps less ambiguous in the OT. According to James Johnson, St Augustine upheld the morality of war itself by contending that “if God can command war, as the Old Testament shows he has done, it cannot be inherently immoral;”³⁷ and St Augustine “finds enough evidence from the New Testament to refute the Manichaeian argument that the New Testament God is a different one.”³⁸

³⁵ MacGregor, “Jesus the Pacifist?,” 29.

³⁶ Grenke, *God, Greed, and Genocide*, 17.

³⁷ James T. Johnson, “St Augustine (354-430 CE),” in *Just War Thinkers: From Cicero to the 21st Century*, ed. Daniel R. Brunstetter and Cian O’Driscoll (Oxon: Routledge, 2018), 24.

³⁸ Johnson, “St Augustine (354-430 CE),” 24.

Thus, St Augustine affirms that the Christian God is the God of the OT and NT. Also, in the NT it is stated that “Jesus Christ the same yesterday, and to day, and for ever.”³⁹ Therefore, there should be continuity as well as coherence in terms of a divine position on warfare, by God, even if God’s timeless divine principles are illustrated from different angles.

One compelling paradox pertains to how the Christian might at times employ violence while not violating the *double love command*,⁴⁰ articulated in the NT. For instance, how could a Christian love his neighbor,⁴¹ while employing violence against the same neighbor in war? St Augustine contemplates the double love command and implies that its ultimate telos is endeavoring “to get his neighbor to love God;” and to strive to “be at peace or in well-ordered concord with all men.”⁴² This line of reasoning seems to expand the implications for the double love command such that a man who loves God must promote God’s will on the earth as in heaven,⁴³ and pertains to dealing with wicked and evil men, sometimes violently, not out of hatred, but out of love, in accordance with God’s revealed truth. Therefore, in the contexts of dealing with evildoers such as the

³⁹ Heb. 13:8 KJV.

⁴⁰ Matt. 22:37-39 KJV.

⁴¹ Matt. 22:39 KJV.

⁴² Saint Augustine of Hippo, *The Essential Augustine*, trans. Vernon J. Bourke (New York, NY: Mentor-Omega Books, 1964), 161.

⁴³ Matt. 6:10 KJV; Matt. 18:18 KJV.

Nazis of WWII, violence employed out of love for innocent victims as well as love of one's own enemy,⁴⁴ with the aim of restoring peace and tranquility to the world which provides the conditions for Christian virtues to flourish.

Adam Hollowell analyzes the twentieth modern *just war* theorist Paul Ramsey and states that Ramsey adhered to a type of "Augustinian moral realism."⁴⁵ Hollowell assesses that "Ramsey argued that violent resistance against the evildoer may be a form of Christian love of neighbor."⁴⁶ Additionally, Hollowell summarizes Ramsey's just war thinking which includes essential concepts such as "discrimination and proportionality,"⁴⁷ as well as "moral limitations on justified war."⁴⁸ For instance, Ramsey was not a nuclear pacifist, per se, yet rejected nuclear stockpiling as disproportionate and morally untenable.⁴⁹ Hollowell states that Ramsey's notion of just war is informed by theological virtues including love, faith, and hope, and "insists that justified war will require prudence, temperance, and courage."⁵⁰ Ramsey's philosophy on Christian just war theory

⁴⁴ Matt. 5:44 KJV; Luke 6:27 KJV.

⁴⁵ Adam Hollowell, "Paul Ramsey (1913-1988)," in *Just War Thinkers: From Cicero to the 21st Century*, ed. Daniel R. Brunstetter and Cian O'Driscoll (Oxon: Routledge, 2018), 193.

⁴⁶ Adam Hollowell, "Paul Ramsey (1913-1988)," in *Just War Thinkers: From Cicero to the 21st Century*, ed. Daniel R. Brunstetter and Cian O'Driscoll (Oxon: Routledge, 2018), 193.

⁴⁷ Hollowell, "Paul Ramsey (1913-1988)," 195.

⁴⁸ Hollowell, "Paul Ramsey (1913-1988)," 195.

⁴⁹ Hollowell, "Paul Ramsey (1913-1988)," 195.

⁵⁰ Hollowell, "Paul Ramsey (1913-1988)," 200.

seems to bring a substantial sense of humanity and restraint to the activity of warfare.

The practice of Christian military strategists grounding the art and science of warfare in the sacred principles revealed by the Christian God is arguably one of the greatest ways that the God might intervene in warfare. It is important to use wisdom when determining when to use violence, but the greater wisdom is arguably the discernment regarding when not to use violence. According to Howard Hensel, just war doctrine is “a matter of conscience for those responsible for deciding whether to resort to the use of armed force,” its legitimacy stems from “the Eternal Order and, ultimately, to the authority of God.”⁵¹ In other words, divine wisdom informs the employment of violence, and the highest wisdom regarding warfare, arguably, flows from God, and Christian just war theorists interpret and actualize this divine wisdom in war.

Christian Justice of War and Justice in War

When is war justified and how must war be carried out humanely to the maximum possible extent? Richard Norman articulates, “the Latin phrases *jus ad bellum* and *jus in bello*. The former is the question of what makes it right *to go to war*. The latter is the question of what it is right to do *in war*, that is, what means of

⁵¹ Howard M. Hensel, “Theocentric Natural Law and Just War Doctrine,” in *The Legitimate Use of Military Force: The Just War Tradition and the Customary Law of Armed Conflict*, ed. Howard M. Hensel (Surrey, UK: Ashgate, 2009), 17.

fighting are permissible.”⁵² Christian just warriors must keep both concepts in mind when deciding to go to war, and when employing violence in warfare.

In terms of the first concept, Howard Hensel defines *jus ad bellum* (justice of war) as “the conditions under which belligerents might justly resort to the use of armed force as a means of conflict resolution.”⁵³ Richard Norman articulates *jus ad bellum* as a set of necessary conditions for a war to be considered a just war, which include factors such as: just cause, right intention, legitimate authority, reasonable hope of success, last resort, and proportionality.⁵⁴ Hensel further articulates the concept of *jus ad bellum* in terms of “theocentric natural law”⁵⁵ as follows: “the cosmopolitan, internationalist perspective emphasizing the common good of all mankind;”⁵⁶ and this view stresses the cessation of hostilities where “the former belligerents... can all reside together in a post-conflict environment, based upon neighborly friendship, cooperation, and harmony, predicated upon a sense of shared goals, coordinated activities, justice, and the common good of all

⁵² Richard Norman, *Ethics, Killing and War* (Cambridge: Great Britain, 1995), 118.

⁵³ Howard M. Hensel, “Theocentric Natural Law and Just War Doctrine,” in *The Legitimate Use of Military Force: The Just War Tradition and the Customary Law of Armed Conflict*, ed. Howard M. Hensel (Surrey, UK: Ashgate, 2009), 5.

⁵⁴ Richard Norman, *Ethics, Killing and War* (Cambridge: Great Britain, 1995), 118.

⁵⁵ Hensel, “Theocentric Natural Law and Just War Doctrine,” 11.

⁵⁶ Hensel, “Theocentric Natural Law and Just War Doctrine,” 11.

peoples.”⁵⁷ Furthermore, these concepts could be seen as divine from the perspective that they altruistically transcend self-centered base human instincts.

In terms of the second concept, Hensel defines *jus in bello* (justice in war) as the just employment of the armed forces at all levels of warfare (from strategic to tactical) “during periods of armed hostilities.”⁵⁸ Furthermore, according to Norman, for *jus in bello* must include two vital factors, which are: that civilians and non-combatants are never intentionally killed; and proportionality must be factored into the judicious use of military force.⁵⁹ More specifically, Hensel further elaborates on the concept of *jus in bello* in Christian terms as follows: “Christian thinkers were emphatic in predicating the category of right intention concerning the actual employment of force upon the qualities of mercy, compassion, and charity to all and the admonition to love one’s neighbor, including one’s enemy, just as one would hope that the enemy would extend the same charity, mercy, and compassion to one’s own combatants and non-combatants.”⁶⁰ Relatedly, the words of Jesus Christ in the NT are as recorded as “Put up again thy sword into his place: for all they that take the sword shall perish with the sword.”⁶¹ Christian just warriors should carefully weigh those words, and strive to put down their swords as soon as

⁵⁷ Hensel, “Theocentric Natural Law and Just War Doctrine,” 11.

⁵⁸ Hensel, “Theocentric Natural Law and Just War Doctrine,” 5.

⁵⁹ Norman, *Ethics, Killing and War*, 119.

⁶⁰ Hensel, “Theocentric Natural Law and Just War Doctrine,” 14.

⁶¹ Matt. 26:52 KJV.

possible, and always strive for peace, whenever, wherever, and as long as ever possible.

Just Cause

One of the most fundamental aspects of Christian just war theory is the concept of a *just cause*. For instance, Gregory Reichberg cites “Aquinas’ *causa justa*”⁶² which is the Latin equivalent. Moreover, according to David Kinsella and Craig Carr, “Aquinas, following St. Augustine, was also concerned that war be guided by *right intention*.”⁶³ The concept of just cause was essential to just war thinkers such as St Augustine and St Aquinas because it compelled Christian warriors to seriously question their own motivations for going to war, to eliminate unholy motives while minimizing the cruelty of war.⁶⁴ According to Kinsella and Carr, St Aquinas perceived the ultimate telos of war as restoring justice, tranquility, and peace.⁶⁵ According to this way of thinking, evils and horrors of war are readily acknowledged and boundaries are established to ensure that war is properly used as a tool of peace.

⁶² Gregory M. Reichberg, “Thomas Aquinas (1224/5-1274),” 61.

⁶³ David Kinsella and Craig L. Carr, “Intervention,” in *The Morality of War: A Reader*, ed. David Kinsella and Craig L. Carr (London, UK: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 2007), 189.

⁶⁴ David Kinsella and Craig L. Carr, “Intervention,” in *The Morality of War: A Reader*, ed. David Kinsella and Craig L. Carr (London, UK: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 2007), 189.

⁶⁵ David Kinsella and Craig L. Carr, “Intervention,” in *The Morality of War: A Reader*, ed. David Kinsella and Craig L. Carr (London, UK: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 2007), 189.

The concept of just cause appears to act as a moral restraint to the activity of war, so that the employment of violence is justified and precisely focused. Gregory and Kegley, contend that for just war theorists: “Just cause and right intention,” are two essential conditions, and “wars fought in self-defense meet these criteria by having a morally good objective and by being waged to correct a serious transgression and re-establish peace and justice.”⁶⁶ Gregory and Kegley contend that in general, “just-war theory... denies the legitimacy of preventive military action;” since “no party should be the judge of its own cause and obscure the boundary between anticipatory self-defense and aggression.”⁶⁷

Preemptive military attacks on potential adversaries are a dilemma and slippery slope. The NT calls Christians to love their neighbors and to love their enemies.⁶⁸ Therefore rushing into preemptive military attacks, arguably, would not appear to allow sufficient reflection on one’s own motives to determine whether one’s cause is just, or provide enough space for Christian love to find alternative options.

⁶⁶ Gregory A. Raymond, and Charles W. Kegley, Jr., “Preemptive and Preventive War,” in *The Legitimate Use of Military Force: The Just War Tradition and the Customary Law of Armed Conflict*,” ed. Howard M. Hensel (Surrey, UK: Ashgate, 2009), 109.

⁶⁷ Raymond and Kegley, “Preemptive and Preventive War,” 109.

⁶⁸ Mark 12:31 KJV; Matt. 5:44 KJV.

The Doctrine of Double Effect

Gregory Reichberg attributes the “doctrine of double effect (DDE).”⁶⁹ In terms of self-defense, St Aquinas finds that “Nothing hinders one act from having two effects, only one of which is intended, while the other is beside the intention.”⁷⁰ In private matters concerning individual citizens, St Aquinas articulates the notion that one man may inadvertently kill the other in self-defense, and be blameless in doing so, if the man defending himself is acting in good faith and his intent is defense rather than killing.⁷¹ In terms of warfare between nations, St Aquinas implies that soldiers do not commit murder in war, if not motivated by personal hatred, but when acting on behalf of governmental authority “for the common good.”⁷² However, are there limits to governmental authority in warfare?

It seems reasonable that public authorities must follow strict ethical guidelines when engaging in warfare. According to David Rodin, “The double-effect principle has traditionally been taken to ground a moral distinction between the deliberate targeting of noncombatants, often called terror bombing, and tactical bombing, which aims at military targets but may cause collateral damage among

⁶⁹ Gregory M. Reichberg, “Thomas Aquinas (1224/5-1274),” in *Just War Thinkers: From Cicero to the 21st Century*, ed. Daniel R. Brunstetter and Cian O’Driscoll (Oxon: Routledge, 2018), 57.

⁷⁰ Saint Thomas Aquinas, *Summa Theologiae*, II-II, Q64. A7.

⁷¹ St Aquinas, ST, II-II, Q64. A7.

⁷² St Aquinas, ST, II-II, Q64. A7.

noncombatants.”⁷³ In the DDE methodology, “The death of noncombatants, while it is a foreseen consequence of the action, is not intended either as a means or as an end.... Provided the requirements of necessity and proportionality are met, therefore, the action, together with its foreseen consequence, is not impermissible.”⁷⁴ At some level, DDE might be akin to Pontius Pilate washing his hands of any guilt while ordering Christ’s Crucifixion, as his ostensible intent was maintaining public order and not the death of Jesus,⁷⁵ even though that specific example is unique and unlike any other. Nevertheless, Christian just warriors who adhere to DDE could be seen as promoting mercy in accordance with the NT divine imperative,⁷⁶ and only employing as much violence as required to accomplish a righteous objective; and not indulging carnage for its own sake.

Christian Warfare, the Nation-State, and Society

In this section, I explore whether violence sanctioned by the state in terms of warfare is compatible with the Christian law of love as revealed in the NT, which includes love of neighbor and love of enemies.⁷⁷ Both Christian just war theorists as well as Christian anti-war pacifists make compelling arguments based

⁷³ David Rodin, “Terrorism Without Intention,” in *The Morality of War: A Reader*, ed. David Kinsella and Craig L. Carr (London, UK: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 2007), 181.

⁷⁴ David Rodin, “Terrorism Without Intention,” in *The Morality of War: A Reader*, ed. David Kinsella and Craig L. Carr (London, UK: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 2007), 181.

⁷⁵ Matt. 27:23-25 KJV.

⁷⁶ Matt. 5:7 KJV.

⁷⁷ Matt. 22:39 KJV; Matt. 5:44 KJV; Luke 6:27 KJV; 1 John 4:7 KJV.

on NT scripture, and both address the divine commandment to love from different angles. The Christian pacifist would claim that any form of violence violates Christian love. By contrast, Christian just war theorists would argue that loving enemies does not preclude the possibility of violence, and sometimes it is necessary to fight the wicked, not motivated by hatred, but by a greater love for humanity which seeks to end injustice and restore peace and harmony to society.

There is a historical argument for Christian pacifism, as the early Christians ostensibly did not engage in violence. According to Richard Norman, “The early Christian church rejected all participation in military activities, but when Christianity became the official religion of the Roman Empire it had to accommodate itself to the realities of political life, and thinkers such as Augustine tried to formulate the conditions under which the waging of war could be consistent with Christian morality. Over the centuries those conditions were more precisely formulated and codified into a body of doctrine which was the official teaching of the Catholic Church.”⁷⁸ However, the notion that the Catholic Church conjured up just war doctrine out of thin air for political expediency may not accurately depict important historical nuances. For instance, the emergence of just war theory did not just spring up out of thin air.

Much depends on one’s interpretative framework. If the Christian God continues to intervene in world events behind the scenes, the Emperor Constantine’s success on the battlefield could have been due to divine intervention

⁷⁸ Norman, *Ethics, Killing and War*, 117.

unto God's aim for the salvation of souls under a regime more sympathetic to Christian beliefs. It was likely linked to the miracles surrounding the miracle of the *cross in the sky* and Emperor Constantine's vision Jesus Christ,⁷⁹ which coincided with Constantine's decisive victory on October 28 312 at the Battle of the Milvian Bridge.⁸⁰ Regarding that historical event, Bishop Eusebius records that, "Constantine suddenly sees a bright cross of light emblazoned against the noonday sky and upon it the inscription: 'In hoc signo vinces' —'In this Sign Conquer.'"⁸¹ Consequently, Constantine commands his soldiers to emblazon their shields with a Greek Christogram⁸² containing the letters *Chi* and *Rho* (*X* and *P*), which are the first two letters of Christ in Greek (i.e., Χριστός).⁸³ From 312 onward until his death Constantine was heavily involved in Christian affairs. In 324 he conquered the Eastern Half of the Roman Empire in a war which was also an ostensible campaign to rescue Eastern Christians from persecution under Licinius.⁸⁴

⁷⁹ Raymond Van Dam, *Remembering Constantine at the Milvian Bridge*, (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011), 11.

⁸⁰ Roger Tomlin, "Christianity and the Late Roman Army," in *Constantine: History, Historiography and Legend*, ed. Samuel N.C. Lieu and Dominic Monsterrat (London: Routledge, 1998), 21.

⁸¹ Christian History Institute, "In Hoc Signo Vinces [In this sign conquer]," Constantine (280–337). Quoted in the Ecclesiastical History of Eusebius. (n.d.), Accessed June 10, 2024, <https://christianhistoryinstitute.org/incontext/article/constantines-cross>.

⁸² Raymond Van Dam, *Remembering Constantine at the Milvian Bridge*, 3.

⁸³ Raymond Van Dam, *Remembering Constantine at the Milvian Bridge*, 3.

⁸⁴ Timothy Barnes, "Constantine, Athanasius and the Christian Church," in *Constantine History, Historiography and Legend*, ed., eds. Samuel N.C. Lieu and Dominic Monsterrat (London: Routledge, 1998), 7.

Barnes articulates that, “in the winter of 312-13 Constantine began a systematic policy of giving honors, privileges and donations to the Christian Church and Christian Clergy.”⁸⁵ Moreover, Constantine, “in 324-5, as the new master of the East, he prohibited the cultic activities which until then had characterised the traditional religions of the Roman empire, and he thus affirmed the status of Christianity as the official religion of the state and its rulers.”⁸⁶ Whether his motivations were based on political savviness or legitimate belief in the Christian God, Constantine left not only an indelible mark on the development and trajectory of the burgeoning Christian faith but on the total entire Roman Empire (West and East) to include an enduring legacy on Western Civilization. Under Constantine, Christianity went from being a persecuted religion to a preferred religion.⁸⁷ From a point of Christian utilitarianism, if God desired the greatest good for humanity, in terms of a society conducive to the flourishing of Christian theological virtues, then the establishment of a Christian government would be a vital step toward that end. Through such an interpretive framework, the use of violence such as Constantine’s battles where he gained control over both halves of the Roman Empire was a necessary violence which, arguably, contributed to a better world closer in alignment with God, albeit imperfect, than would have otherwise been the case had Constantine not taken up arms.

⁸⁵ Barnes, “Constantine, Athanasius and the Christian Church,” 7.

⁸⁶ Barnes, “Constantine, Athanasius and the Christian Church,” 7.

⁸⁷ Barnes, “Constantine, Athanasius and the Christian Church,” 7.

In response to Christian pacifists who contend that the NT outlaws war, R.E.O. White points out that, “Calvin replies: the ancient reason for war still exists; there is no reason for debarring magistrates from defending those under them; the apostolic writings set out the kingdom of Christ, not civil polity; Christ’s coming did not change the situation in this respect.”⁸⁸ Furthermore, White provides the following, “In Calvin’s view church and State are united in seeking to produce a Christian society under God’s sovereign law. The State, hardly less than the church, is an instrument in the hands of God to save the world.”⁸⁹ Moreover, even if Christian pacifism might apply to individuals in their personal lives, it likely does not restrain sovereign governments from utilizing violence, for example, when required to defend the state from outside aggression. For instance, Normal L. Geisler points out that both the OT and NT of the Holy Bible demonstrate how “government is ordained by God,”⁹⁰ and the biblical activist position contends, “that one ought to respond to the government’s call to take part in war because God has given the authority of the sword to the governing authorities.”⁹¹ It is also logical that God, as part of a comprehensive strategy to align the world to God’s

⁸⁸ R.E.O. White, *Christian Ethics* (Trowbridge, GB: Redwood Books, 1994), 210.

⁸⁹ White, *Christian Ethic*, 210.

⁹⁰ Normal L. Geisler, *Christian Ethics: Contemporary Issues & Options*, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2010), 220-222. Regarding the Old Testament Geisler cites authority given to Adam, i.e., “have dominion over... every living thing that moves upon the earth,” Gen. 1:28 RSV, et al.; and regarding the New Testament cites Jesus, “give to Caesar what is Caesar’s;” Matt. 22:21; “You would have no power over me if it were not given to you from above,” John 19:11, et al.

⁹¹ Geisler, *Christian Ethics*, 222.

will, would be concerned with the conversion of societies, governments, and civil authorities, as well as with the conversion of individuals.

Nevertheless, Christian governments are arguably endowed with greater power and authority from God, and thus have greater legitimacy than individuals in terms of the use of violence, when necessary, which fosters a peaceful telos for society. According to James Johnson, “for Augustine the soldier’s killing of enemies is morally possible, since the soldier is not acting out of his own self-love but is obeying superior orders: the soldier’s action can thus be taken without wrong desire.”⁹² Additionally, Johnson contends that St Augustine relentlessly argued for the necessity of war and its justice, grounded in the notion that, “the natural order has been corrupted by sin, with temporal law itself a product of sin, so that God has to step in to seek to reshape this and restore justice in the world.”⁹³ Additionally, there may be times when failure of governments to act to curb wickedness, may be due to fecklessness, but under the guise of Christian pacifism. On the flip side, Christian regimes that are too eager to use violence may be at risk of falling into a form of aggressive Christian nationalism. Therefore, it is likely necessary that Christian just warriors need to employ careful reason and wisdom, finding a sort of Golden Mean⁹⁴ which avoids extremes, when considering the use of violence.

This sort of discernment may be applied to the decision-making process that was arguably influenced by Christian ethics to a great degree during both

⁹² Johnson, “St Augustine (354-430 CE),” 31.

⁹³ Johnson, “St Augustine (354-430 CE),” 24.

⁹⁴ Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, 118, 252-253.

world wars. Criticisms may be applied on both ends. On one hand, criticism may be applied for a failure to act, to use violence to end injustice. On the other hand, criticism may be applied to an enthusiasm to use violence without exhausting all other alternatives, such as diplomatic means. According to Stuart Bell, the Church of England was “uncritical”⁹⁵ of the necessity to take up arms in the First World War, and that there was “virtual unanimity of the Church on the moral justification for the conflict.”⁹⁶ Moreover, Bell points out that “The cult of the martyr-soldier, his sacrifice in the cause of good comparable with that of Christ on the cross, found fresh expression in the commemoration of the war and of the fallen.”⁹⁷ Hence, the Christian impetus to resort to violence in World War I could be questioned based on excessive eagerness to go to war.

By contrast, the opposite criticism may be applied to Christian warriors in the context of World War II. According to Parker and Lawson, the Church of England maintained a position of pacifism during the 1930s amidst the rising threat from Nazi Germany, while at the same time “Church attendance was declining, and the certainties of Anglican theology had collapsed in little more than a

⁹⁵ Stuart Bell, “The Church and the First World War,” in *God and War: The Church of England and Armed Conflict in the Twentieth Century*, ed. Stephen G. Parker and Tom Lawson, (Surrey, England: Ashgate Publishing Limited, 2012), 57.

⁹⁶ Bell, “The Church and the First World War,” 57.

⁹⁷ Bell, “The Church and the First World War,” 58. Bell further indicates that scriptures which buttress this notion adorn British war memorials, such as John 14:13, i.e., “Greater love hath no man than this that he lay down his life for his friends.”

generation.”⁹⁸ However, that does not necessarily imply that declining church attendance and deteriorating doctrine directly manifested as pacifism, per se, as correlation does not necessarily mean causation.

Nevertheless, it is interesting to note that *lukewarm* Christians can at the same time be pacifists, which provides at least one anecdotal example that Christian pacifism as such may not necessarily result from a staunchly pious emulation of Jesus Christ’s pacifism as recorded in the Gospels.⁹⁹ Rather, Christian pacifism may just as likely result from Christian apathy or be grounded in secular reasoning, such as worldly comforts, as well as slothfulness or even cowardice. Assessing motivations is critical to the decision to take up arms or shirking taking up arms, under a type of pseudo piety, even when the cause is noble and just.

However, according to Parker and Lawson, Anglican Church attendance skyrocketed during the Second World War as it took on a robust wartime function as “the wider population subscribed to a type of folkloric Christianity,” even if “doctrinally empty” in certain respects.¹⁰⁰ While it cannot automatically be assumed that increasing church attendance leads to *better* Christianity, per se, as state religion may take on nationalistic overtones which may even be seen to contradict fundamental Christian doctrine at times; it could nonetheless be stated

⁹⁸ Stephen G. Parker and Tom Lawson, *God and War: The Church of England and Armed Conflict in the Twentieth Century* (Surrey, England: Ashgate Publishing Limited, 2012), 4.

⁹⁹ Matt. 26:52 KJV.

¹⁰⁰ Parker and Lawson, *God and War*, 5.

that people tend to get more religious during hard times. Hard times such as an existential crisis seems to have a way of fostering a sense of sober realism.

One way God could intervene in warfare is through His servants, i.e., Kings, Presidents, Prime Ministers, and Generals would read God's revealed truths in scripture, i.e., the Holy Bible, and apply that wisdom to statecraft and warfare. One way that this might be evident in the example of the Second World War is how the divine imperative found in Matthew 5:7, i.e., "Blessed are the merciful: for they shall obtain mercy."¹⁰¹ For instance as applied to warfare this means only use as much force as is required to achieve an objective, e.g., the unconditional surrender of the enemy. The necessity for Christian just warriors to employ wisdom with respect to the use of violence, while avoiding the extremes of militant nationalism under the guise of Christian righteousness, or slothful cowardice under the pretense of Christian pacifism cannot be understated.

A Christian Leader and the Decision to Drop Atomic Bombs in WWII

The decision to drop atomic bombs on Japan to hasten its surrender and end the war presents a compelling case study for Christian just war theorists. While the U.S. is a secular country it has strong Christian foundations and the top U.S. politicians have overtly mixed Christianity into governmental policy from the beginning and the Second World War was no exception. For instance, historical records indicate that President Harry S. Truman was a devout Christian and read the Bible daily as a source of

¹⁰¹ Matt. 5:7, KJV.

inspiration and wisdom.¹⁰² This begs the following question. How could a devout Christian choose to drop two atomic bombs on Japan, and reconcile the horrors of atomic warfare on innocent civilian populations and at the same time consider himself to be an upright follower of the Jesus Christ revealed in the NT?

Elizabeth Anscombe of the University of Oxford issued a scathing rebuke against President Truman's decision to drop atomic bombs on Japan at the end of the Second World War in her 1956 published opposition to Truman's honorary degree from Oxford.¹⁰³ Anscombe's argument characterized Truman's decision as brash and reckless, and that the ends could not justify the means in terms of extreme suffering experienced by innocent civilian victims of the atomic bombs.¹⁰⁴ The answer which might justify Truman's decision lies in essential concepts in the Christian just war tradition including just cause, proportionality, and DDE. While Anscombe is right to focus on the suffering of those impacted by the atomic bombs, she fails to articulate the greater context of the war, including the gruesome nature of the mass atrocities and their magnitude (particularly against civilian populations) as the Japanese Army raped and plundered its way across Asia prior to and during the Second World War.¹⁰⁵ Anscombe issued her

¹⁰² Gary Scott Smith, "Harry S. Truman: The Golden Rule President," *Religion in the Oval Office: The Religious Lives of American Presidents* (New York, 2015; online edn, Oxford Academic, 19 Mar. 2015).

¹⁰³ Anscombe, Elizabeth, *Mr. Truman's degree* (Oxford: Oxonian Press, 1956), 3; A. L. Rowse, "Our Anglo-Saxon Legacy: A British View," *Current History* 31, no. 184 (1956), 337.

¹⁰⁴ Anscombe, *Mr. Truman's degree*, 1-3.

¹⁰⁵ Yuki Tanaka, *Hidden horrors: Japanese war crimes in World War II* (New York: Routledge, 2019).

rebuke of Truman nearly a decade after the end of the war and under the blanket of stability and security provided to her by the blood and sacrifice of many thousands of Allied soldiers as they put an end to brutal fascist regimes in Europe and Asia. Thus, Anscombe criticizes Truman in a decontextualized, and arguably, unfair manner.

The context under which violence is employed appears to be an essential aspect of Christian just war theory. Relatedly, Michael Walzer frames Truman's decision to drop atomic bombs on Japan through the lens of proportionality. Walzer articulates that Truman's advisors assessed that if the war were to drag on into 1946 America could have suffered another million casualties in addition to a substantially higher number of Japanese casualties (based on the casualties incurred to capture Okinawa in the spring of 1945, i.e., 80,000 Americans and 120,000 Japanese).¹⁰⁶ The calculus was based on the small size of Okinawa relative to mainland Japan.

Nevertheless, Walzer, tacitly acknowledges the casualties from Nazi genocide, while providing precise numbers of German and Japanese civilians killed by Allied fire-bombing, and from atomic bombs, and contends that: the combined Axis civilian deaths "from Allied terrorism in World War II must have exceeded half a million men, women, and children."¹⁰⁷ Walzer asks "How could the initial choice of this ultimate weapon ever have been defended?"¹⁰⁸

¹⁰⁶ Michael Walzer, "Supreme Emergency," in *The Morality of War: A Reader*, ed. David Kinsella and Craig L. Carr (London, UK: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 2007), 262.

¹⁰⁷ Walzer, "Supreme Emergency," 254.

¹⁰⁸ Walzer, "Supreme Emergency," 254.

Similarly to Anscombe, Walzer's rebuke of Allied bombing during WWII calling it "terrorism"¹⁰⁹ is only tenable by brushing aside the total number of casualties and the causation of the war itself. It was in fact the Axis powers who initiated WWII and were committed to massive death operations against innocent civilians in terms of the Nazi Holocaust in Europe and the Japanese murderous rampage in Asia. From a Christian just war paradigm, even Truman's choice to use atomic bombs could perhaps be justified on the grounds of just cause, proportionality, necessity, DDE, and an earnest desire to hasten the restoration of peace in the world. The humane treatment of Germany, Italy, and Japan, post-war, by the victorious Allies seems to buttress that position.

Concluding Analysis on Christian Just War Theory vs. Christian Pacifism

When examining Christian arguments for just warfare and pacifism, it is important to apply wisdom and discernment. Both concepts are *right* in the context of when they are rightly applied. Christian just warriors who are too quick to hastily pick up the sword without proper discernment might be just as wrong as Christian pacifists who would stand idly by refusing to take up the sword and allowing wicked men to commit heinous atrocities against innocent and defenseless people. Correspondingly, St Augustine contends that, anyone who considers human nature will see that everyone desires both joy and peace; that even those who wage war seek peace through victory; that wars are fought to achieve peace, not for the

¹⁰⁹ Walzer, "Supreme Emergency," 254.

sake of war itself; and those who disrupt peace only do so to create a peace that better suits them.¹¹⁰

Accordingly, it seems ironic that all men desire peace. Therefore, war is fundamentally a tool to reshape the world and its situation according to one's own ideology or paradigm. Even the Nazis wanted peace, but their 'peace' would have been a very miserable world indeed. The point is that does God intervene to shape the world or prevent the worst possible world from coming to fruition? It could be argued that Christian just warriors who are solidly grounded in proper Christian ethics as revealed in the OT and NT are in a sense, proxies who help shape the world in accordance with God's divine will.

Subsequently, the use of violence is sometimes a necessary evil which is required to promote a greater good. For instance, Richard Norman, addresses the notion of "*absolute* moral principles," which are "principles which specify that certain kinds of actions are always right or wrong, whatever the consequences."¹¹¹ For example, according to Norman, if applying an absolute moral principle to according to "The taking of human life," and considering such an action morally wrong in all circumstances, then "it would commit one to absolute pacifism."¹¹² However, Norman states that when nuances change due to additional caveats then

¹¹⁰ Saint Augustine of Hippo, *The Essential Augustine*, trans. Vernon J. Bourke (New York, NY: Mentor-Omega Books, 1964), 213.

¹¹¹ Richard Norman, *Ethics, Killing and War* (Cambridge: Great Britain, 1995), 74.

¹¹² Norman, *Ethics, Killing and War*, 74.

allowances can be made which move one to a different paradigm.¹¹³ For instance, Norman articulates that adding the word ‘innocent’ to the context of taking human life can fundamentally change the conditions that would allow one to take human life;¹¹⁴ and this alternated paradigm allows for the traditional view held by the Roman Catholic Church which allows for killing enemy combatants in war, killing belligerents in self-defense, and the execution of killing criminals as justice.¹¹⁵

Therefore, discerning wisdom allows one to see when violence is justified. Geisler points to the merits of Christian just war activists and anti-war pacifists have valid perspectives: “The activists are right in pointing out that God has ordained the government and given it the sword. They are correct in insisting on human obedience to government, even at times to the point of taking life. However, the pacifists are right that we should pursue peace and try to live peaceably with all people. We should be peacemakers, not warmakers. And we should resort to war only when all efforts at peace fail rather than wait to try peace when all efforts at war fail.”¹¹⁶ According to Norman, existential crises have a way of fostering a type of sober realism, such that a “consequential pacifist might, for example, have said in 1939: ‘Confronted with the historical record, I have until now held the view that war never achieves sufficient good to justify the enormous moral prices that has to

¹¹³ Norman, *Ethics, Killing and War*, 74.

¹¹⁴ Norman, *Ethics, Killing and War*, 74.

¹¹⁵ Norman, *Ethics, Killing and War*, 74.

¹¹⁶ Geisler, *Christian Ethics*, 242.

be paid, but we now face, in Nazism, a quite unprecedentedly evil regime, and even the terrors of war are likely to be outweighed by the horrors of allowing this regime to continue.”¹¹⁷ Hence, the wisdom to know when to apply violence and when to refrain from its use is divine knowledge, and both schools of Christian just war theory and Christian pacifism have substantial insights to offer which emanate from the sacred texts of the OT and NT which are ostensibly revealed knowledge by the Christian God.

In the next section, I take a closer look at the violence in the OT by examining through the lens of just war theory, in a search for indications of divine restraint regarding God’s revealed involvement in warfare, which may further illustrate coherent connections with the NT in terms of conditions where divine violence is demonstrated.

Examining God’s Intervention in Warfare in the Old Testament

Here, I examine the topic of divine intervention in warfare in the OT and identify whether divine violence is coherent with the concepts identified in the previous section. Regarding divine intervention in warfare in the OT, Paul Copan identifies some characteristics of the wars approved by the Israelite God as follows: 1) restricted in geographical scope to the Promised Land; 2) pertaining to particular historical generations; 3) unambiguous objectives focused on egregious moral wickedness; 4) at times God’s love and mercy extends to historical adversaries of Israel; 5) God’s commands are grounded in love; and 6) God establishes

¹¹⁷ Norman, *Ethics, Killing and War*, 75.

normativity in war which pertains to a covenantal relationship with a select group of chosen people.¹¹⁸ These factors set the stage for the circumstances and characteristics surrounding divine intervention in warfare in the OT.

It is also noteworthy that the problem of “divine hiddenness,”¹¹⁹ as articulated by naturalists such as J.L. Schellenberg, does not appear to be a problem for the OT, which if true, depicts a God who is anything but hidden in warfare. There is perhaps no more obvious example of divine intervention in warfare than the events described in the Book of Exodus regarding miracles worked by God through Moses to protect Hebrew slaves from a violent onslaught by the Egyptian Pharaoh’s military forces.¹²⁰ If these events are to be taken seriously as actual historical events, what might they reveal about God’s intervention in warfare?

For example, after the Pharaoh released the Hebrew slaves allowing them to leave Egypt, he later led his military forces to slaughter them; and God worked unambiguous miracles through Moses in ways that directly vanquished the Pharaoh’s armed men and charioteers.¹²¹ Just because the Hebrew slaves were unarmed does not mean they were not in a state of war with Egypt, as wars are often asymmetrical, as one side is slaughtered by the other which wields greater power. The Egyptian side was at war against the Hebrew slaves, attempting to

¹¹⁸ Paul Copan, *Is God a Moral Monster?: Making Sense of the Old Testament God* (Grand Rapids: Baker Books, 2011), 205-206; Jer. 31; Ezek. 36.

¹¹⁹ J.L. Shellenberg, “Divine hiddenness and human philosophy,” in *Hidden Divinity and Religious Beliefs: New Perspectives*, ed. Adam Green and Eleonore Stump (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 16.

¹²⁰ Exod. Chs. 14-15 KJV.

¹²¹ Exod. 14:24-25 KJV; Exod. 15:1-4 KJV.

annihilate them by military force.¹²² I would argue that the story is likely credible. I based that on the notion of power. From a worldly perspective, the Egyptians had all the power, while the Hebrews had none. The account in Exodus articulates the divine power of God acting in such a way as to reverse the asymmetry, and dramatically so, in favor of the Hebrew slaves. I would not be so quick to attribute those events as embellished natural phenomena, and I will address the metaphysics of divine intervention in a later section.

While the parting and collapse of the Red Sea is arguably the most depicted divine intervention miracle in contemporary popular culture, there are arguably at least three divine interventions recorded in Exodus, which depict a comprehensive strategy as opposed to a one-off miracle. There appear to be at least three divine interventions in this story. The first miracle was a pillar of fire which created a buffer between the Egyptian soldiers and the Hebrew slaves fleeing for their lives. The second was the collapse of the Red Sea which had been supernaturally parted to create a pathway for the fleeing Hebrews, and then collapsed to entomb the Egyptian soldiers in the sea to prevent their continued murderous assault against the Hebrews. These are: 1) "the angel of God, which went before the camp of Israel, removed and went behind them; and the pillar of the cloud went from before their face, and stood behind them:"¹²³ 2) "the pillar of fire" which "troubled the host of the Egyptians"¹²⁴ and 3) the parting and collapse of the Red Sea which

¹²² Exod. 14:7-9 KJV; 14:17-18 KJV.

¹²³ Exod. 14:19 KJV.

¹²⁴ Exod. 14:24 KJV.

allowed the Children of Israel to walk on dry land safely, but swallowed up the Egyptian forces which were not allowed to pursue and utterly destroyed.¹²⁵

The events described in Exodus provide powerful imagery in the struggle of marginalized and oppressed peoples and could arguably be identified as the leading example from the ancient world of antislavery and the advancement of human rights. If so, this seems to illustrate divine ethics bestowed in tandem with divine intervention, and perhaps demonstrate a holistic pattern by the OT God. In terms of the OT, specifically Exodus, David Brown articulates the notion of “Liberation theology” contained in Exodus which has modern day applicability, in terms of liberating “the poor and oppressed.”¹²⁶ In such ways, the ethical framework embodied by Moses provides a social and ethical framework revealed by the God of the OT in addition to divine intervention in the form of miracles which helped liberate the Hebrews from Egyptian control. Thus, such examples help shed light on the fact that if God does intervene in warfare in miraculous ways, then one hallmark of such intervention might be divine justice which fortifies the weak and humble against exploitation of the strong and powerful. This sort of interpretive framework might provide a connecting thread from the events in Exodus found in the OT to the *Sermon on the Mount*¹²⁷ recorded in the NT and shows God’s coherence throughout the Holy Bible.

¹²⁵ Exod. 14:26-31 KJV; Exod. 15:1-4 KJV.

¹²⁶ David Brown, “The Context: Theology and Ethics,” in *War and Peace*, ed. Jeff Astley, David Brown, and Ann Loades (London, UK: T&T Clark, 2003), 9.

¹²⁷ Matt. Ch. 5; Luke Ch. 6.

On one hand it could be said that the events described in Exodus are at worst merely myths and legends, and at best, based on actual events but dramatically embellished in a way as to not be taken seriously in terms of historical accuracy. Alternatively, what if the fantastical events described in the OT occurred in the way they are described regarding warfare? What then could be gleaned in terms of God's reasons for intervening in warfare? If the events described in Exodus really happened then one interpretation regarding God's strategy is that it appears that God exercised tremendous restraint, and harm to the Egyptians was seemingly passive and a graduated proportional response to Egyptian aggression. For instance, the pillar of fire could have just burnt up the Egyptian forces but was only used defensively to create a protective buffer between them and the Hebrews. God later allowing them in the Red Sea also appears to be defensive in nature, ostensibly due to a second buffer of water, and worth noting that it was only due to Egyptian foolish hubris which would continue militant pursuit under such circumstances.

Moreover, the events at Passover which claimed the lives of the Egyptian first born was arguably also a preemptive proportionate response to Pharaoh's intent to wipe out the first born children of the Hebrews.¹²⁸ In any event, the divine intervention on behalf of the Hebrews freedom from bondage in Egypt seems to indicate a coherent rational and proportional strategy, and divine violence not

¹²⁸ Exod. 12:29 KJV.

inflicting for its own sake but as necessary and proportionate as required to achieve specific strategic objectives.

One might find problems with the notion of God's intervention in warfare on multiple levels. For instance, did God sanction genocide in the OT as critics such as notorious atheist professor Richard Dawkins have pointed out?¹²⁹ For instance, there are specific OT examples.¹³⁰ On the other hand, critics could also point to God's seeming inaction in preventing the Holocaust during the Second World War. This seems to be paradoxical. On one hand, God is charged with sanctioning genocide in the OT, while seemingly fails to stop genocide in modern times. Thus, in the OT there does not appear to be the same problem of divine hiddenness as in modern times. It could therefore be argued that the God of the OT is a human projection and conveniently used as an impetus for genocidal maniacs to fulfill their own desires, while the absence of God during the Holocaust could further buttress the notion that God simply does not exist. On the other hand, it could be argued that God does intervene under certain conditions (and not always overtly) and imposes limitations on God's own intervention due to various factors such as free will.

There are various criticisms of the methods of God of the OT. For example, Richard Dawkins uses a variety of slanderous verbiage to describe the God of the OT, some of which include, "vindictive, bloodthirsty... misogynistic,

¹²⁹ Richard Dawkins, *The God Delusion* (London: Bantam Press, 2006), 51.

¹³⁰ Num. 13, 14, 31; Josh. 1-6.

homophobic, racist, infanticidal, genocidal, filicidal, pestilential,”¹³¹ etc., and Arthur Grenke opines that the God of the OT unambiguously sanctions war on behalf of the Israelites for genocidal purposes, e.g., for the “destruction,”¹³² and “annihilation of the idolaters,”¹³³ and the “Israelite conquest of the Holy Land,”¹³⁴ which he argues forged a template for subsequent types of genocidal regimes even into modern times.¹³⁵

According to Grenke, the God of Israel, i.e., Yahweh, was fundamentally different from deities found in other ancient cultures, such that he could chastise or bless, which put the Israelites in a position of avoiding punishment and seeking to procure blessings.¹³⁶ Since he was seen as the one and only true ruler of the cosmos, the Israelite people sought to garner His favor through strict observance of their God’s divine laws and commands.¹³⁷ This paradigm included violence as much as necessary to eliminate any competing groups of people to prevent any form of cross pollination with *wicked* peoples or *false* religions.¹³⁸

¹³¹ Dawkins, *The God Delusion*, 2006, 51.

¹³² Arthur Grenke, *God, Greed, and Genocide: The Holocaust Through The Centuries*, (Washington, D.C.: New Academia Publishing, 2005), 17.

¹³³ Grenke, *God, Greed, and Genocide*, 17.

¹³⁴ Grenke, *God, Greed, and Genocide*, 18.

¹³⁵ Grenke, *God, Greed, and Genocide*, 17-18.

¹³⁶ Grenke, *God, Greed, and Genocide*, 19.

¹³⁷ Grenke, *God, Greed, and Genocide*, 19.

¹³⁸ Grenke, *God, Greed, and Genocide*, 31.

Pierre Winandy “We, as theologians, should be the humblest of scholars. Why? Because as finite, imperfect, and sinful beings, we dare to investigate the infinite, perfect, and infallible God! And this God has consented to reveal Himself in a written document, the Bible. Under the guidance of the Holy Spirit it is our privilege to explore the inspired information. An attempt to understand the problem of God and war in the Old Testament is still more daring, and we must feel even more humble.”¹³⁹ According to Winandy, in the Old Testament “God’s ideal plan,”¹⁴⁰ was revealed in various contexts “when Israel was confronted with enemies.”¹⁴¹ Winandy makes observations about “God’s Battle Strategy”¹⁴² and points out that in the case of assisting Gideon to defeat the Midianite army “without any armed intervention by Gideon’s soldiers,”¹⁴³ but only the divinely wielded trumpets which caused violent disarray within its own ranks.¹⁴⁴ This is quite a critical observation and shows the God of the Old Testament in an entirely different light than that portrayed by critics of the OT

¹³⁹ Pierre Winandy, “God and War in the Old Testament,” *Journal of the Adventist Theological Society* 9, no. 1 (1998): 318.

¹⁴⁰ Winandy, “God and War in the Old Testament,” 318.

¹⁴¹ Winandy, “God and War in the Old Testament,” 318-320. Some of Winandy’s examples include: a) God is attributed to fighting the Egyptians including removing their chariot wheels, Exod. 14:25; b) “The Lord your God, who is going before you, will fight for you, as he did for you in Egypt” Deut. 1:30; and c) When a Midianite army means to attack Gideon, by the LORD’s divine power the sound of the three hundred trumpeters caused the Midianite soldiers to turn their swords on each other and flee in disarray, Judg. 7:7, 16, 22.

¹⁴² Winandy, “God and War in the Old Testament,” 319.

¹⁴³ Winandy, “God and War in the Old Testament,” 319.

¹⁴⁴ Winandy, “God and War in the Old Testament,” 319; Judg. 7:22.

God such as Richard Dawkins.¹⁴⁵ For instance, the pillar of fire which blocked the Egyptian advance toward the fleeing Hebrew slaves seems to demonstrate tremendous non-violent, and passive restraint while at the same time showing the awesome power of God. It also could indicate God's love by a reluctance to harm or inflict injury and doing so only when necessary. God seems to demonstrate proportionality and the use of violence only when necessary to accomplish an objective, and only as much as is required to realize that objective. In other words, God does not seem to indulge in violence for its own sake, and manifests divinely reasoned violence.

According to Winandy, in the OT there are wars that God permits against the Israelites when they ignore God's plan.¹⁴⁶ Winandy also claims that the Old Testament contains examples of "Wars God Ordered,"¹⁴⁷ which includes the divine command for Israelites to make war against the Canaanites.¹⁴⁸ Winandy contends that "The ideal plan of God: The Lord will fight for you. Just trust and obey, and He will deliver you. The fulfillment in history: When the leaders and the people trusted God, He delivered them."¹⁴⁹ Winandy fundamentally contends that the God of the OT employs war at various levels as one mechanism to bring His children, i.e., the Israelites back into a right

¹⁴⁵ Dawkins, *The God Delusion*, 2006, 51.

¹⁴⁶ Winandy, "God and War in the Old Testament," 320. Winandy cites the war between the Israelites and Amalekites described in Exod. 17:8-9.

¹⁴⁷ Winandy, "God and War in the Old Testament," 322.

¹⁴⁸ Winandy, "God and War in the Old Testament," 322. Winandy cites Judg. 1:1-2.

¹⁴⁹ Winandy, "God and War in the Old Testament," 324.

relationship with God to include obeying His plan for their ultimate telos and flourishing, e.g., “when the people trusted God, He delivered them.”¹⁵⁰ God’s ways, at times, may seem cruel by human standards. However, divine intervention in the OT seems to occur out of God’s superior knowledge, wisdom, and ultimate telos for God’s children, for their ultimate flourishing. Therefore, God’s intervention may come across as cruel from a certain vantage point. The Pharaoh of Egypt would likely have seen the complete destruction of his soldiers as they were swallowed up by the Red Sea as cruel. Even so, God arguably cannot be judged by human standards. Isaiah illustrates this sentiment in the following: “Let the wicked forsake his way, and the unrighteous man his thoughts: and let him return unto the LORD, and he will have mercy upon him; and to our God, for he will abundantly pardon. For my thoughts *are* not your thoughts, neither *are* your ways my ways, saith the LORD. For *as* the heavens are higher than the earth, so are my ways higher than your ways, and my thoughts than your thoughts.”¹⁵¹ God’s wrath and mercy contained in the OT may at times seem paradoxical but makes more sense during careful analysis of the context wherein each divine attribute is exhibited, and this sort of ethos of divine violence arguably extends to the God of the NT as well.

The answer may reside in God’s multidimensionality and ineffable nature. Nonetheless, the “Flatland” analogy may be helpful to theologians reflecting on various attributes of God’s character which at times may seem contradictory: “when a sphere passes through Flatland, what appears in the experience of the

¹⁵⁰ Winandy, “God and War in the Old Testament,” 325.

¹⁵¹ Isa. 55:7-9.

Flatlanders is a circle.”¹⁵² Subsequently, two-dimensional beings would see a sphere but only as a circle, as they would only be able to perceive the portion which connects with a two-dimensional plane. Thus, Jesus Christ reveals that his teachings contained in the NT are inextricably interconnected to revealed wisdom of the OT: “Think not that I am come to destroy the law, or the prophets: I am not come to destroy, but to fulfil [*sic*].”¹⁵³ Moreover, in the Gospel of Luke the Lord opens the minds of his disciples so that they know all of the Old Testament prophecies were talking about him.¹⁵⁴ Hence, the argument is that the God of the OT is the same as the God of the NT, and so both texts should be evaluated holistically when examining God’s divine intervention in warfare.

Therefore, in the following section, I examine the ways in which the use of violence is still permissible with the ethics revealed in the NT, and the Augustinian Christian just war paradigm addresses how divine love can be reconciled with the use of violence in the context of divine justice. This shows how either God could intervene in warfare, or God’s proxies on the earth can righteously use violence without contradicting God’s moral laws or good nature.

In the next section I explore the metaphysical possibility of divine intervention in warfare and examine how this might manifest within the context of biblical accounts. The Old Testament provides numerous examples of God’s direct

¹⁵² Adonis Vidu, *The Divine Missions: An Introduction* (Eugene, OR: Wipf and Stock Publishers, 2021), 57.

¹⁵³ Matt. 5:17. KJV.

¹⁵⁴ Luke 24:44-45 KJV.

involvement in warfare, which can serve as case studies for understanding how divine intervention has been historically understood within the Judeo-Christian tradition. By looking at these events, we can better appreciate the coherence between the metaphysical model and how it might be applied to biblical narratives.

Looking at the Metaphysics of Divine Intervention:

How Might God Intervene in Warfare?

The Christian God who directly intervenes, at times, in human affairs stands in contrast to the god articulated in Deism who created the universe and does not intervene in human affairs. For instance, deist Thomas Paine gives no credit to the Holy Bible, and affirms a type of ‘unknown’ God who creates the universe but does not reveal truth to humanity in scripture, e.g., “The creation is the Bible of the Deist.”¹⁵⁵ By contrast, Benedikt Paul Göcke articulates a “metaphysical model of special divine intervention,”¹⁵⁶ as revealed in the Christian Holy Bible, as follows: “that God acts in the world on special occasions in order to guarantee the success of His providential plans in such a way that, counterfactually, had God not acted, then the course of nature would have been different. A special act of divine intervention thus is God’s actualisation of a state of affairs that otherwise would not have occurred.”¹⁵⁷ This model addresses how the miraculous

¹⁵⁵ Thomas Paine, *The age of reason*, (New-York: Wright & Owen, 1831), 154, eBook Collection, The Making of the Modern World, https://encore.st-andrews.ac.uk/iii/encore/record/C__Rb2120796.

¹⁵⁶ Benedikt Paul Göcke, “Did god do it? Metaphysical models and theological hermeneutics,” *International Journal for Philosophy of Religion* 78 no. 2 (Oct 2015): 223, DOI 10.1007/s11153-014-9489-7.

¹⁵⁷ Göcke, “Did god do it?,” 223.

events described in the Holy Bible might have actually taken place from a scientific point of view.

Moreover, in exploring the mechanics of how God might perform miracles in the physical world, Benedikt Göcke asks, “Did God Do It?”¹⁵⁸ and articulates “a metaphysical model according to which God can realize acts of special divine providence by way of temporarily changing the dispositions of natural entities.”¹⁵⁹

Göcke argues that, “the laws of nature are generalizations that derive from the dispensational behavior of natural kinds.”¹⁶⁰

Citing both OT and NT examples, Göcke points out that the Christian tradition is grounded in the notion that God intervenes as necessary in the world so as to “guarantee the success of His providential plan.”¹⁶¹ Göcke, describes two problems with divine intervention which pertain to the law of nature: 1) *ontological determinism*, i.e., the laws of nature are fixed in such a way as to not allow special outside divine intervention, and 2) *casual closure*, i.e., divine intervention could not be possible “because the laws of nature entail that the actual world is causally closed.”¹⁶² However, Göcke contends that recent gains in scientific knowledge with respect to quantum mechanics could solve these problems and potentially show how the Christian God could very well have intervened

¹⁵⁸ Göcke, “Did god do it?,” 215.

¹⁵⁹ Göcke, “Did god do it?,” 215.

¹⁶⁰ Göcke, “Did god do it?,” 215.

¹⁶¹ Göcke, “Did god do it?,” 215-216. Examples provided include OT: “the Exodus from Egypt;” and NT: “the founding of the church at Pentecost.”

¹⁶² Göcke, “Did god do it?,” 216.

“in the history of the world.”¹⁶³ Göcke applies his metaphysical model to the parting of the Red Sea, and contends God is not restricted by the laws of nature which are not independent variables, nor immutable, but are subject to God’s will.¹⁶⁴ Thus, “to separate the Red Sea, God does not have to violate any law of nature, putatively existing in an abstract realm of ontological regulative force, but only has to change the disposition of a well-defined number of water-molecules that at the time constitute the corresponding parts of the Red Sea.”¹⁶⁵ Finally, Göcke contends his metaphysical model contributes to hermeneutical advances depicting a world history that has been shaped by “a God acts on special occasions,” and buttresses an “overall Christian worldview.”¹⁶⁶ Göcke’s work is compelling because it illustrates in modern scientific language how God might have intervened in history, and his model could be applied as an explanatory lens for the ostensible miracles recorded in both the OT and NT. In St Mark’s Gospel it is recorded that, “With men *it is* impossible, but not with God: for with God all things are possible.”¹⁶⁷ The metaphysics of divine intervention sheds light on how divine intervention might take place.

The metaphysical model might be applied to specific events in world history where divine providence is seen as having changed the trajectory of world events.

¹⁶³ Göcke, “Did god do it?,” 217.

¹⁶⁴ Göcke, “Did god do it?,” 223; Exod. 14:21 KJV.

¹⁶⁵ Göcke, “Did god do it?,” 223; Exod. 14:21 KJV.

¹⁶⁶ Göcke, “Did god do it?,” 228-229.

¹⁶⁷ Mark 10:27 KJV.

Monumental events that may fit into this may include: 1) the *miracle* of the Cross in the Sky at the Battle of the Milvian Bridge in 312 which coincided with the victory of the Emperor Constantine;¹⁶⁸ or 2) the anomalous fierce storm that destroyed the Spanish Armada that attempted to invade Britain in 1588, and sustained the Protestant reign of Elizabeth I.¹⁶⁹ These events could be attributed to random probability on one hand. However, Thomas Hobbes interprets such events through the lens of theistic political theory, illustrates that God's use of and purpose of miracles is to provide divine legitimacy to God's chosen rulers who fulfill a divine commission as proxies who carry out God's divine will on the earth: "The nature of a miracle, that it be wrought for the procuring of credit to God's messengers, ministers, and prophets, that thereby men may know, they are called, sent, and employed by God, and thereby be the better inclined to obey them."¹⁷⁰ If Hobbes' contention is true then it may buttress arguments regarding why God might intervene in human affairs.

In the next section I explore another area in the supernatural or metaphysical realms in terms of what intelligences can be obtained from the immortal soul in terms of near-death experiences. While novel and perhaps a bit unorthodox, I assess this information to potentially be of great value in assessing the overall research question.

¹⁶⁸ Van Dam, *Remembering Constantine at the Milvian Bridge*, 11; Tomlin, "Christianity and the Late Roman Army," 21.

¹⁶⁹ Erin Riddiford, "The Elizabethan Sea," *INTAGLIO: University of Toronto Art Journal* 1, (Spring 2019): 84; John Guy, *The reign of Elizabeth I: Court and culture in the last decade* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1995), 205.

¹⁷⁰ Thomas Hobbes, *Leviathan: Or the Matter, Forme and Power of a Commonwealth Ecclesiastical and Civil*, ed. Michael Oakeshott (New York, NY: Simon & Schuster, 1962), 343.

God and Warfare:

Potential Intelligence Obtained from a Christian Near-Death Experience

In addition to exegetical study of the scriptures, and the philosophical study of Christian warfare ethics, another useful source of intelligence with regard to God's position on warfare may come in the form of revealed knowledge as a result of Christian near-death experiences. Arguably, the first Christian NDE could be recorded in the NT as described by St Paul as follows: "It is not expedient for me doubtless to glory. I will come to visions and revelations of the Lord. I knew a man in Christ above fourteen years ago, (whether in the body, I cannot tell; or whether out of the body, I cannot tell: God knoweth;) such an one caught up to the third heaven. And I knew such a man, (whether in the body, or out of the body, I cannot tell: God knoweth;). How he was caught up into paradise, and heard unspeakable words, which it is not lawful for a man to utter."¹⁷¹ St Paul continues to describe a conversation with Jesus Christ in this state as follows: "For this thing I besought the Lord thrice, that it might depart from me. And he said unto me, My grace is sufficient for thee: for my strength is made perfect in weakness. Most gladly therefore will I rather glory in my infirmities, that the power of Christ may rest upon me."¹⁷² Therefore, it seems that St Paul might have received divine knowledge from Jesus Christ while outside the body, which could be interpreted as an NDE.

¹⁷¹ 2 Cor. 12:1-4 KJV.

¹⁷² 2 Cor. 12:8-9 KJV.

This begs the question, are such divine experiences limited to the saints and apostles as recorded in the Bible, or does God as Jesus Christ, still bestow divine knowledge during Christian NDEs? According to Dr. Jeffrey Long’s peer reviewed study of thousands of NDEs spanning more than three decades is published by a peer-reviewed medical journal, and states that “nine lines of evidence provides powerful evidence that NDEs are, in a word, real.”¹⁷³ A good number of those NDEs are Christian in nature and reflect experiences of Jesus Christ as God. In particular, the following Christian NDE reveals specific information regarding God’s position on warfare.

The Christian NDE of Howard Storm is perhaps one of the most reliable and vetted NDE accounts having his story in the public domain for decades—having been interviewed by many reputable journalists investigate¹⁷⁴—and having renowned author Anne Rice leverage her own clout to publish and promote Storm’s book about his NDE.¹⁷⁵ Storm’s NDE occurred in Paris in 1985, when Storm, a tenured university art professor was escorting his students on an European

¹⁷³ Jeffrey J. Long, “Near-death experience. Evidence for their reality,” *Missouri medicine* 111, no. 5 (2014): 379.

¹⁷⁴ Howard Storm, *My Descent into Death: And the Message of Love Which Brought Me Back*, ed. (West Hoathly, UK: Clairview Books, 2012), L2.

¹⁷⁵ Carol Memmott. 2024. “Vampire Author Rice Gives Lift to Pastor’s ‘Descent.’” *USA Today* (McClean), Feb 22, 2005, EBSCO Connect. Storm’s NDE is arguably one of the most well-known Christian NDEs of the last half-century, widely disseminated in the public domain and featured by multiple reputable news agencies.

Art tour.¹⁷⁶ Howard Storm died in a Paris hospital due to a perforation in his small stomach as a surgeon was unavailable in time to treat his acute condition.¹⁷⁷

Storm describes himself as a baptized Christian in childhood but became a militant existentialist atheist as he grew older and accumulated worldly status and accolades.¹⁷⁸ He initially describes a horrific encounter with demonic creatures that deceived him and led him on a long trek toward a place of total darkness.¹⁷⁹ They eventually turned on him, and he describes the horror as hundreds of these creatures tore him to mercilessly and viciously attacked him in unspeakable ways.¹⁸⁰ As his emaciated and shredded body lay on the ground an inner voice called to him three times, “Pray to God!”¹⁸¹ He initially thought this was a ridiculous idea still defiant in his atheism.¹⁸² He eventually cobbled together crude prayers to include the pledge of allegiance and anything that he could remember with the word God.¹⁸³ As he did so the creatures screamed, appeared tortured by the mere mention of God, and eventually fled from him.¹⁸⁴

¹⁷⁶ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 3, 5, 85.

¹⁷⁷ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 4, 87.

¹⁷⁸ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 11, 23, 65.

¹⁷⁹ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 19, 20.

¹⁸⁰ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 19-22.

¹⁸¹ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 23.

¹⁸² Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 23.

¹⁸³ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 23.

¹⁸⁴ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 24.

Finally in bloodied desperation lying in a fetal position on the ground in total darkness, Storm cried out, “Jesus save me.”¹⁸⁵ When he did, Howard states that Jesus rushed toward him as being an exceptionally bright light, healed him, and took him to heaven where Christ and angels gave Storm a life review and answered any question that Howard had by literally downloading an encyclopedia of divine knowledge into his mind.¹⁸⁶ Storm states that he was free to ask any question to Jesus and the angels, so he asked “why there had been wars.”¹⁸⁷ The response was “quick and emphatic;” that “God hates war. God has no desire for you to use violence and destructive means for you to assert your will over one another. But God allows wars to happen when you are determined to be at war. God has influenced you in the course of your history to find more peaceful methods to resolve your differences. The vast majority of wars that you have desired have not taken place because God has subtly influenced people to prevent war. There have been occasions when God has let you suffer the consequences of your desire for war.”¹⁸⁸

Howard Storm reports that another dimension to the answer was when Storm asked how God could have allowed the World War II Holocaust.¹⁸⁹ As part

¹⁸⁵ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 29.

¹⁸⁶ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 97-104, 158.

¹⁸⁷ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 106.

¹⁸⁸ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 106.

¹⁸⁹ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 109.

of the answer, Jesus reportedly placed Storm in a WWII concentration camp where Jewish prisoners were being taken from railway cars, and witnessed the savage treatment which culminated in human extermination.¹⁹⁰ Storm describes his own weeping as he witnessed a scene depicting Nazi camp guards talking about the “Angel maker” as “piles of naked corpses being loaded into ovens.”¹⁹¹ Storm then states, “Then Jesus said to me, ‘These are the people God loves.’ Then he said, ‘Look up.’ Rising out of the smoke of the chimneys I saw hundreds of people being met by thousands of angels taking them up into the sky... how ironic that the guards sarcastically called the ovens ‘the Angel maker.’”¹⁹² Such a gruesome scene certainly, does raise what many scholars such as Alvin Plantinga wrestle with, namely the “problem of evil”¹⁹³ and how it could be that a God who is both benevolent and omnipotent tolerates the existence of evil in the world.¹⁹⁴ During his NDE experience when Storm was shown the extermination scene in the Nazi camp, he asked Jesus and the angels, “how God could allow this to happen.”¹⁹⁵ The answer was, “this was not God’s will. This was an abomination to God. God wants this to never happen again... This holocaust was breaking God’s heart.”¹⁹⁶

¹⁹⁰ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 109.

¹⁹¹ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 109.

¹⁹² Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 109.

¹⁹³ Alvin Plantinga, *God, Freedom, and Evil* (London: George Allen & Unwin Ltd, 1974), 7.

¹⁹⁴ Plantinga, *God, Freedom, and Evil*, 9-10.

¹⁹⁵ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 109.

¹⁹⁶ Storm, *My Descent into Death*, 109.

Nevertheless, there is a tension between God's good desire for the world, and the evil which God permits out of his love for creaturely freedom. As Plantinga puts it, Plantinga articulates the "Free Will Defense"¹⁹⁷ in the following terms: "Now God can create free creatures, but He can't *cause* or *determine* them to do only what is right. For if He does so, then they aren't significantly free after all; they do not do what is right *freely*. To create creatures capable of *moral good*, therefore, He must create creatures capable of moral evil; and He can't give these creatures the freedom to perform evil and at the same time prevent them from doing so."¹⁹⁸

Alvin Plantinga articulates that, "The fact that free creatures sometimes go wrong, however, counts neither against God's omnipotence nor against His goodness; for He could have forestalled the occurrence of moral evil only by removing the possibility of moral good."¹⁹⁹

As horrific as the Holocaust was, if the intelligence gathered in this NDE is true, then it provides some hope, in that all accounts are settled in the next life. As is stated in scripture, "it is appointed unto men once to die, but after this the judgment."²⁰⁰ Thus, the guilty will be punished and the innocent comforted as is described in the Gospel of Luke concerning the rich man who died and ended up in

¹⁹⁷ Plantinga, *God, Freedom, and Evil*, 29.

¹⁹⁸ Plantinga, *God, Freedom, and Evil*, 30.

¹⁹⁹ Alvin Plantinga, *God, Freedom, and Evil* (London: George Allen & Unwin Ltd, 1974), 30.

²⁰⁰ Heb. 9:27.

hell, while the poor beggar ended up being comforted in heaven in the afterlife.²⁰¹

Moreover, in Revelation of the NT it is stated that, “God shall wipe away all tears from their eyes; and there shall be no more death, neither sorrow, nor crying, neither shall there be any more pain: for the former things are passed away.”²⁰²

Wickedness on the earth is due to human faults, and only permitted by God’s allowance for free will. As Alvin Plantinga states, human free will is of great value to God.

Nevertheless, scripture indicates that all will be held accountable e.g., “And as it is appointed unto men once to die, but after this the judgment:”²⁰³

Moreover, regarding divine judgment it is revealed that, “For we must all appear before the judgment seat of Christ; that every one may receive the things *done* in *his* body, according to that he hath done, whether *it be* good or bad.”²⁰⁴

If the information contained in Howard Storm’s NDE is true regarding God’s position on warfare, then one conclusion is that God, who hates war, might allow war, but at the same time may intervene on behalf of the side that is established in Christian just war principles. That is the side that is *merciful*,²⁰⁵ and desires a quick cessation of war, and with the least amount of human suffering as

²⁰¹ Luke 16:22-23 KJV.

²⁰² Rev. 21:4 KJV.

²⁰³ Heb. 9:27 KJV.

²⁰⁴ 2 Cor. 5:10 KJV.

²⁰⁵ Matt. 5:7 KJV.

possible. St Augustine, opines on evil and “the privation of the good,”²⁰⁶ as follows:

By the Trinity, thus supremely and equally and unchangeably good, all things were created; and these are not supremely and equally and unchangeably good, but yet they are good, even taken separately. Taken as a whole, however, they are very good, because their ensemble constitutes the universe in all its wonderful order and beauty. And in the universe, even that which is called evil, when it is regulated and put in its own place, only enhances our admiration of the good; for we enjoy and value the good more when we compare it with the evil. For the Almighty God, who, as even the heathen acknowledge, has supreme power over all things, behind Himself supremely good, would never permit the existence of anything evil among His works, if He were not so omnipotent and good that He can bring good even out of evil. For what is that which we call evil but the absence of good?²⁰⁷

How could Howard Storm’s NDE revelations be relevant to God and warfare? The following scripture articulates that, “And we know that all things work together for good to them that love God, to them who are called according to *his* purpose.”²⁰⁸ Therefore, under such an interpretive framework, modern NDEs are possibly another credible source of continuing divine revelation.

In the next sections I will examine the possibility of divine intervention in modern warfare.

²⁰⁶ Saint Augustine of Hippo, *The Essential Augustine*, trans. Vernon J. Bourke (New York, NY: Mentor-Omega Books, 1964), 65.

²⁰⁷ Saint Augustine of Hippo, *The Essential Augustine*, trans. Vernon J. Bourke (New York, NY: Mentor-Omega Books, 1964), 65.

²⁰⁸ Rom. 8:28 KJV.

World War I Case Study:

Sergeant Alvin York, A Christian Conscientious Objector Turned War Hero

Alvin York was an American soldier in the First World War. York converted to Christianity in 1915. He was deeply conflicted and torn apart by a sense of duty and patriotism to his country on the one hand, and on the other by the of Christian pacifism which would oppose any form of killing and an ardent opposition to war.²⁰⁹

York received his notice to register for the draft in June of 1917 which was a non-voluntary government order to enlist in the Army. York sought a religious exemption on the grounds of being a “conscientious objector” on religious grounds as a Christian pacifist.²¹⁰ York ended up filing four separate appeals with authorities in Tennessee and all were denied on the grounds that York’s church “had no creed except the Bible, a book subject to conflicting interpretations.”²¹¹

According to Lee, York continued to be tormented by the morality of war which he felt violated his Christian convictions and eventually disclosed his concerns to his superiors when York “was assigned to Company G, 328th Infantry, Eighty-second Division, a combat unit that seemed destined for front-line

²⁰⁹ David D. Lee, *Sergeant York: An American Hero* (Lexington, KY: The University Press of Kentucky, 1985), 16.

²¹⁰ Lee, *Sergeant York: An American Hero*, 17.

²¹¹ Lee, *Sergeant York: An American Hero*, 17.

service.”²¹² York’s battalion commander Major George Edward Buxton together with York:

Spent a long night discussing the Bible’s teachings concerning war. The major began quoting Christ’s admonition, ‘He that hath not sword, let him sell his cloak and buy one’ (Luke 22:36), and asked York if Christ who drove the moneychangers from the temple would ignore German ‘war crimes’ in Belgium. He pointed out that Jesus had told his followers, ‘For my kingdom is not of this world, but if my kingdom were of this world, then would my servants fight’ (John 18:36). Buxton argued that the United States was an earthly government due the ‘things that are Caesar’s’ and therefore Christian servants of that government should fight for its preservation. He ended by reading a long passage from Ezekiel (33:1-6) that suggested that the Lord expected his people to defend themselves.²¹³

Major Buxton had promised York a non-combat assignment in the Army should York remain steadfast in his Christian pacifism.²¹⁴ Nevertheless, York reportedly spent a later night in prayer and solitude on a mountain which resulted in a massive change of heart.²¹⁵ According to Lee, York changed his mind about participating in a combat role; “That night on the mountain, York experienced, in effect, a second conversion, returning home convinced that God wanted him to fight and would preserve him unharmed in battle.”²¹⁶ These events appear to have given York an unshakable confidence and resolve to fully commit himself to the war. “In February 1919, an investigation was conducted to see if York’s action of 8

²¹² Lee, *Sergeant York: An American Hero*, 19.

²¹³ Lee, *Sergeant York: An American Hero*, 19.

²¹⁴ Lee, *Sergeant York: An American Hero*, 19.

²¹⁵ Lee, *Sergeant York: An American Hero*, 19-20.

²¹⁶ Lee, *Sergeant York: An American Hero*, 20.

October 1918 merited the Medal of Honor. While walking the ground with York, Brigadier General Lindsey asked him, ‘York, how did you do it?’ To which, Alvin answered, ‘It was not man-power but it was divine power that saved me.’ Lindsey, moved by York’s comments, put his arms around York’s shoulders and said in a low voice, ‘York, you are right.’”²¹⁷

On 8 October 1918, at the Battle of Argonne, Sergeant York, unharmed, and with a single rifle, destroyed multiple enemy machine guns, killed more than 20 German soldiers, and captured 132 German soldiers.²¹⁸ “Interestingly, despite receiving these high awards, York never wrote home about them or what he did on 8 October. Instead, his letters discussed the farm, planting season, discourses on the health of the animals, and the like. Such humility tends to say a lot about his character.”²¹⁹ Correspondingly, R.E.O White opines that, “The single exception which Calvin allows to the ‘private’ Christian’s duty of submission to civil authority — that such obedience shall not transgress the law of God — is crucially tested in time of war, when civic duties imposed may sharply conflict with Christian conscience.”²²⁰ Alvin York’s experience, while originally grounded in

²¹⁷ Douglas V. Mastriano, *Alvin York: A New Biography of the Hero of the Argonne* (Lexington, KY: University Press of Kentucky, 2014), 138.

²¹⁸ Mastriano, *Alvin York: Hero of the Argonne*, 121-139; “1918 U.S. Soldier Alvin York displays heroics at Argonne,” History, Accessed, June 15, 2024.

²¹⁹ Mastriano, *Alvin York: Hero of the Argonne*, 141.

²²⁰ R.E.O. White, *Christian Ethics* (Trowbridge, GB: Redwood Books, 1994), 209.

Christian pacifism, seems to epitomize the noblest virtues from the just war tradition.

In the next section I explore the possibility of God's divine intervention in warfare for humanitarian purposes to ease suffering.

World War II Case Study:

Capt. Louis Zamperini, Fulfilling a Promise to the Christian God

Lieutenant Louis Zamperini, aka "Louie," was a U.S. Army Air Forces bombardier in the Pacific during World War II.²²¹ His experience directly and intimately relates to invoking God during the war to save him and his men as they helplessly drifted on the open ocean in a life raft.²²² Zamperini overcame astronomical odds dodging death in several precarious situations throughout the war.²²³ His amazing survival could be relegated to mere chance on the one hand. However, on the other hand, when examining each event that ensured his survival through another lens, the case could be made for divine intervention by God who Zamperini invoked.²²⁴ If true, this could shed light on how God could work in warfare to respond to those who are suffering and who beseech God for assistance when all other hope is lost. It could be that the severe and desperate nature of

²²¹ Laura Hillenbrand, *Unbroken: An Extraordinary True Story of Courage and Survival* (London, GB: Fourth Estate, 2011), 11, 75, and 403, eBook, EPUB (Fife Libraries). Zamperini was a Lieutenant and promoted to the rank of Captain during his time in a prisoner of war camp in Japan during the war.

²²² Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 190.

²²³ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 155, 162, 186, 194, 425, 437, et al.

²²⁴ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 190.

warfare creates the absolute humility and brokenness of spirit that may reach God's heavenly throne. For instance, this sort of sentiment is captured in scripture, e.g., "The sacrifices of God *are* a broken spirit: a broken and a contrite heart, O God, thou wilt not despise."²²⁵ Zamperini found himself in such dire circumstances during the war which could possibly explain how God might have responded in salvific ways to protect and sustain him during his many tribulations.

I find Louie Zamperini's recollections of his wartime experiences to be highly credible. For instance, prior to the war, Zamperini was an Olympian who competed in the 1936 Berlin Olympics,²²⁶ and broke multiple national running records at the high school, college, and Olympic levels.²²⁷ Being a commissioned officer as a Lieutenant would have placed him in the 80th percentile of military ranks and being a wartime bombardier would have required a tremendous amount of vetting and training. In short, Zamperini's credible wartime recollection comes from a disciplined and sober mind. There is also no indication that his recollection of divine intervention during the war is distorted, or that his post-war Christianization, including returning to Japan to forgive his former captors, could be attributed to a motive for fame or fortune.²²⁸ His forgiveness was unconditional,

²²⁵ Ps. 51:57 KJV.

²²⁶ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 54. After one of his running matches at the 1936 Olympics, Louie was escorted to the Führer's box where they shook hands and Hitler's comments in German were relayed by an interpreter, "Ah, you're the boy with the fast finish."

²²⁷ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 29, 32, 33, 35, 54. University of Southern California (USC).

²²⁸ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 190, 485.

but simply asked them to become Christians.²²⁹ For instance, his biography including his wartime saga was not written by Laura Hillenbrand until 2010,²³⁰ years after Louie had spent decades in carrying out Christian non-profit philanthropic service beginning in 1954,²³¹ and he running as a torch bearer in the 1998 Winter Olympics in Nagano, Japan.²³² He was already well-known as the “Torrance Tornado” due to his accomplishments as a professional runner.²³³ It seems far more likely that extreme hardship during the war, including open ocean survival and years of intense beatings and forced labor in a Japanese prisoner of war camp placed an indelible mark on him, and his postwar act of giving his life to Christ appears to be genuine, and after recovering from trauma and remembering the vow he had made to God years earlier when he was drifting in the Pacific Ocean during the war.²³⁴

Louie miraculously escaped from death multiple times during the war. The first time was when his aircraft malfunctioned over the Pacific Ocean while it was on a search and rescue mission, and crash landed on the open ocean.²³⁵ After his

²²⁹ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 485.

²³⁰ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 3.

²³¹ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 4.

²³² Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 476.

²³³ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 35-45.

²³⁴ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 190.

²³⁵ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 154.

bomber plummeted onto the surface of the ocean and began to sink rapidly, Louis was stuck inside, temporarily knocked unconscious and held captive by strands of electrical wiring that had wrapped around him as the plane was submerged in water.²³⁶ When he regained consciousness, he found himself in complete darkness, yet all of the wires that had been tightly woven around him were miraculously loosened and he was able to escape from the aircraft during its rapid descent into the ocean abyss.²³⁷

Only three men survived the crash landing and had managed to procure only two rubber boats from the airplane which had almost no survival equipment or provisions.²³⁸ Despite this fact, Louie and Phil had managed to break the world record for raft survival, by surviving for 46-days on the open ocean.²³⁹ One night on the open ocean Louie reported to his friend Phil, onboard the raft, hearing an angelic choir over his head as if all of heaven was watching over them.²⁴⁰

One miraculous divine intervention possibly occurred when their rafts were spotted by an overhead Japanese bomber.²⁴¹ The bomber dropped low strafing the rafts with a barrage of machine guns fired on multiple passes; and each time the

²³⁶ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 155-156.

²³⁷ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 156.

²³⁸ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 159-163.

²³⁹ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 211.

²⁴⁰ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 210.

²⁴¹ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 12, 198, 458.

men jumped out of the rafts to escape the bullets they had to simultaneously deal with the shark infested waters, the creatures that had encircled them for days.²⁴² The Japanese bomber crew was determined to kill the desperate men as they lay helpless at the mercy of the open ocean. This vicious attack destroyed one raft and left the other with multiple holes which the men worked tirelessly to patch over multiple days as the men took shifts patching while continuously, sleeplessly pumping out water from the raft over multiple days.²⁴³ By random chance or divine intervention, none of the men were hit with a single bullet, and they managed to stabilize one of two rafts.²⁴⁴

One of their greatest threats to survival was dehydration. For instance, “On the sixth day without water, then men recognized that they weren’t going to last much longer. Mac was failing especially quickly. They bowed their heads as Louie prayed. If God would quench their thirst, he vowed, he’d dedicate his life to him. The next day, by divine intervention or fickle humors of the tropics, the sky broke open and rain poured down. Twice more the water ran out, twice more they prayed, and twice more the rain came. The showers gave them enough water to last a short while longer.”²⁴⁵ While the connection between prayer and a shift in personal circumstances could be attributed to random probability, or even luck from a

²⁴² Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 12, 198, 458.

²⁴³ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 12, 197.

²⁴⁴ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 191-199.

²⁴⁵ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 190.

secular perspective, there is a precedent in the Christian tradition to attribute sustenance in terms of the manifestation of food or drink in various forms under specific conditions to divine intervention.²⁴⁶

Zamperini was later captured by a Japanese naval vessel and spent years in a prisoner of war camp near Tokyo where he was always on the brink of death, due to forced labor, starvation, and regular vicious beatings.²⁴⁷ Once the Japanese found out Louie was an Olympic athlete they tried to use him to broadcast anti-American propaganda by radio; Louie refused.²⁴⁸

When Louie made it back home after the war he struggled with intensive post-traumatic stress syndrome and alcoholism.²⁴⁹ He nearly choked his pregnant wife to death in the middle of the night, mistaking her for one of his Japanese captors.²⁵⁰ Louie later gave his life to Christ at a Billy Graham event in Southern California.²⁵¹ That night, Billy Graham said, “God works miracles one after another... God says, ‘If you suffer, I’ll give you the grace to go forward.’”²⁵² Then Louie remembered the vow he made to God on that open ocean many years earlier,

²⁴⁶ Matt. 15:32-38; John 2:6-11; John 4:7-14.

²⁴⁷ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 232-362.

²⁴⁸ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 336.

²⁴⁹ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 426, 446.

²⁵⁰ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 449.

²⁵¹ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 459-460.

²⁵² Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 458.

and the numerous ways he should have died during the war, but had a realization that God's grace had miraculously preserved him through every trial when the odds were overwhelmingly stacked against him by circumstances.²⁵³ Louie subsequently gave his entire life to Christ that night,²⁵⁴ and went on to forgive his wartime captors, i.e., the sadistic Japanese jailors who had viciously tormented him.²⁵⁵ He later returned to Japan on a mission to forgive every camp official who had harmed him, and he asked them to become Christians.²⁵⁶

Louie Zamperini is a fascinating case study which shows how God might intervene in warfare in humanitarian situations, when God is invoked by those who are suffering and in need. This could technically include any Christian soldier who finds himself in need to include humanitarian and survival situations during wartime. Such mercy might be extended beyond limitations of national alliances, as any follower of Christ is a citizen of heaven. Jesus Christ in the Sermon on the Mount states, "Blessed *are* they that mourn: for they shall be comforted."²⁵⁷ If true, this could mean that God intervenes in war to ease its suffering, and when directly invoked God could intervene in humanitarian situations e.g., giving water to those

²⁵³ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 458-459.

²⁵⁴ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 460.

²⁵⁵ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 485.

²⁵⁶ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 485.

²⁵⁷ Matt. 5:4 KJV.

who thirst,²⁵⁸ or comfort to those who mourn.²⁵⁹ Particularly, on that open ocean Louie and his men had no weapons and were no longer combatants and it would not have been lawful to shoot them as had been attempted by the Japanese bomber.²⁶⁰

Moreover, God might have used Louie to show the model for Christian longsuffering, magnanimity, and forgiveness, following the example of Jesus Christ, i.e., “love your enemies, bless them that curse you, do good to them that hate you, and pray for them which despitefully use you, and persecute you.”²⁶¹ Zamperini did that, and in his treatment of former wartime enemies, exemplified Christian love which brought about reconciliation and healing amongst peoples, and nations formerly at war. Zamperini carried the Olympic Torch in the 1998 Nagano Japan Olympics.²⁶²

²⁵⁸ John 4:14 KJV. In this verse Jesus gives water to the Samaritan woman at the well which transcends ethnic or national boundaries as she was not Jewish. The woman was surprised that Jesus would have any dealings with her as a Samaritan woman as described in John 4:9 KJV.

²⁵⁹ Matt. 5:4 KJV.

²⁶⁰ Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 217.

²⁶¹ Matt. 5:44 KJV.

²⁶² Hillenbrand, *Unbroken*, 486.

Conclusion

There is a dialectical tension between Christian just war theorists and Christian pacifists. Pacifists like Richard Hays contend that any form of violence is incompatible with the God of the NT as embodied in the example of Jesus Christ.²⁶³ By contrast, Christian just war theorists such as Nigel Biggar refutes the contention that the NT disallows all forms of Christian violence based on the notion that, God is “prepared to respond to incorrigible sinners (should there be any) by authorizing their deaths, not at all because he wants them dead, but because he wants to secure the fulfillment of creation, and because he cannot have the latter without the former.”²⁶⁴ In other words, God must deal with the problem of evil in order to be true to God’s all holy and all just nature.²⁶⁵ If the latter argument for Christian just war theory is tenable, then it opens the doors for divine violence, either by God through supernatural divine means, or by servants of God who act properly in accordance with divine principles revealed by God. This position has been strongly established for centuries under the Augustinian just war tradition.

Regarding divine violence, St Augustine, pontificates about God’s will and dealing with evil in the following terms: “In His supreme will resides the power which acts on the wills of all created spirits, helping the good, judging the evil, controlling all, granting power to some, not granting it to others. For, as He is the creator of all natures, so also is He the bestower of all powers, not of all wills; for

²⁶³ Hays, *Moral Vision of the New Testament*, 319-20.

²⁶⁴ Biggar, "Specify and Distinguish!," 182.

²⁶⁵ 1 Pet. 1:16 KJV; Rom. 3:26 KJV.

wicked wills are not from Him, being contrary to nature, which is from Him.”²⁶⁶ If the Augustinian tradition is tenable, then it validates the possibility of God’s divine intervention in warfare from an ethical standpoint.

The OT and NT of the Holy Bible record fantastical events that point to God’s pattern of involvement in human affairs. This dissertation has attempted to identify certain patterns and establish basic inferences regarding whether God intervenes in warfare. Analysis of selected passages of the Holy Bible is one essential way to address this question which this dissertation has addressed, even though it only scratches the surface of the amount of additional exegesis that could be done on this topic. This work has explored the ethics of warfare to see if God could intervene in warfare without contradicting God’s own principles, namely the law of love. I contend that the Augustinian just war theory and associated principles articulate a response when sufficiently contrasted with Christian pacifism to provide nuance and context.

I have examined a metaphysic model for divine intervention which articulates in scientific terms how divine intervention might occur in warfare, and initial research in this area is compelling. This dissertation has also examined a modern Christian NDE by providing a tie to scripture which might illustrate a precedent for NDEs as recorded in the NT; it is also buttressed by contemporary medical scientific research on the topic. I find NDE research to be thought

²⁶⁶ Saint Augustine of Hippo, *The Essential Augustine*, trans. Vernon J. Bourke (New York, NY: Mentor-Omega Books, 1964), 61-62.

provoking, a potential source of intelligence on the topic, and it might provide useful insights regarding future research on theological topics.

I have examined two case studies of Christian soldiers in the context of modern warfare, one from WWI and another from WWII. The first illustrates how divine intervention might work to protect soldiers who act to uphold the law of love in warfare; Christian just warriors who seek to capture rather than kill, and who focus on justified military objectives to hasten war's end rather than indulging in revenge or bloodlust. The second case study articulates how divine intervention in warfare might occur in terms of humanitarian assistance in dire situations. Conclusions drawn from this data might be swayed by individual interpretative frameworks and informed by ideological beliefs regarding Christianity and violence. In this dissertation, I have evaluated holy scripture and multiple sources of intelligence outside of scripture to assess the *why* and the *how* of God's potential intervention in warfare. This endeavor is multidimensional and multifaceted, and the nature of the question requires examination from multiple angles while making use of orthodox and unorthodox sources.

In summary, the question of whether God intervenes in warfare is multifaceted, requiring a deep analysis of both divine justice and mercy as revealed in the Bible. Christian just war theory, grounded in both the Old and New Testaments, offers a framework for understanding how divine intervention might manifest, whether through the actions of leaders acting in accordance with God's will or through direct divine acts. The tension between divine violence and divine love must be reconciled within the larger context of God's ultimate plan for

creation, where sometimes violence may serve the greater purpose of restoring justice and peace. Pacifism, while a powerful reflection of Christ's teachings, must also be understood in light of the realities of human sin and the need for justice. Therefore, the Christian must carefully discern when violence is necessary, always seeking peace but recognizing that in a fallen world, divine intervention in warfare may serve as a tool for achieving a greater good.

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